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Aims & Scope

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry (*J Endod Restor Dent*) is a highly respected scientific journal that caters to the needs of those interested in the fields of endodontics and restorative dentistry. This online-only journal follows a rigorous and independent peer-review process, ensuring that all articles are unbiased and of the highest quality. The double-blinded approach employed by Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry further strengthens its credibility, making it a trusted source of information for researchers, practitioners, and students alike. With its biannual release schedule, readers can look forward to two new issues each year, in March and September. Overall, Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest developments in these important areas of dental science.

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry provides extensive coverage of both clinical and experimental studies on all aspects of endodontics and restorative dentistry. Notably, the journal features original articles, reviews on current topics, case reports, editorial comments, and letters to the editor that follow ethical guidelines. It is important to note that the journal is published solely in English, ensuring it maintains a global reach and fosters international collaboration within the field.

The journal's editorial and publication processes are meticulously designed to meet the highest standards of integrity and quality. To ensure this, the journal adheres to the guidelines set by several reputable organizations such as the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), World Association of Medical Editors (WAME), Council of Science Editors (CSE), Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), European Association of Science Editors (EASE), and National Information Standards Organization (NISO). Furthermore, the journal is committed to upholding the Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing, which have been laid out by the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) at doaj.org/bestpractice.

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Original Article

Apical Micro-cracks Following Root Canal Preparation, Obturation, and Retreatment with Rotary and Reciprocating Instruments: An In-Vitro Study

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Both continuous rotation and reciprocating systems can be used without a notable difference in dentinal integrity, providing flexibility in clinical decision-making. precise application protocols.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to evaluate apical cracks occurring after root canal preparation and retreatment using different NiTi rotary systems with either continuous rotation or reciprocating motion.

Materials and Methods: A total of 40 freshly extracted single rooted teeth could were used in this study, teeth were divided into 2 main groups (n=20) for each. Group A was prepared with continuous rotation motion (Revo-S). Group B was prepared with reciprocation motion (Wave One). Both groups were divided into two subgroups. Subgroup I was retreated by continuous rotation motion (R-Endo). Subgroup II was retreated by reciprocation motion (Wave One). All teeth were trimmed 1 mm apically then scanned by digital stereomicroscope preparation, after root canal preparation, after obturation and after retreatment procedure. Chi-square test was used to compare between two groups in non-related samples Friedman test was used to compare between more than two groups in related samples. Wilcoxon test was used to compare between two groups in related samples.

Results: No significant difference between continuous rotation motion and reciprocation motion in producing apical cracks during root canal preparation and retreatment procedure was found (p>0.05).

Conclusion: Reciprocating motion resulted in a slightly higher number of apical cracks than continuous rotation, but the difference was not statistically significant.

1. Introduction

Many factors before, during or after endodontic treatment may lead to deterioration of the tooth structure. These factors may include age-related structural changes, such as craze lines on enamel, chemo-mechanical preparation, intra-canal dressings, as well as obturation and restorative procedures.¹ The risk of root fracture is closely linked to the extent of apical canal preparation, the degree of canal enlargement, and the approach used to manage procedural errors, which often serve as focal points for stress accumulation.² It has been suggested that the progression of these dentinal defects may contribute to adverse outcomes, including the development of vertical root fractures.³

The Revo-S system (Micro Mega, Besançon, France) is a Nickel-Titanium (NiTi) rotary instrumentation system comprising six files: SC1, SC2, SU, AS30, AS35, and AS40. Its unique asymmetrical cross-sectional design enables a snake-like motion within the canal, which contributes to its high resistance to cyclic fatigue. This design also facilitates a brushing action against the lateral canal walls, aiding in effective circumferential preparation. Furthermore, the system is characterized by enhanced flexibility, superior centering capability, and minimal canal transportation.⁴

M-wire alloy NiTi material with superelastic wire has good flexible properties than that made from conventional NiTi wire. Thus, such flexibility of reciprocating file might have been contributed to the less number of dentinal defects formation as compared to rotation files.⁵ Wave One (Dentsply Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) is a single file NiTi system made of M-wire alloy. It needs less time to prepare the root canal. It has a triangular or modified triangular cross-section. The clockwise and counterclockwise motions produce reciprocating motion which is

responsible for decreasing cyclic fatigue and stress.¹

The use of rigid stainless steel instruments in curved root canals has been associated with iatrogenic alterations to the original canal anatomy. To mitigate these risks, nickel-titanium (NiTi) instruments were introduced, offering shape memory and superelastic properties that enable safer and more effective navigation of curved canals.⁶ Unfortunately, NiTi rotary file systems have also been associated with dentinal defects, including cracks, during shaping and retreatment procedures.^{6,7} The potential for these defects varies depending on the kinematics of the instrument. Some studies suggest that reciprocating instruments may lead to fewer complete cracks compared to continuous rotation systems, though conflicting findings exist.^{8,9} This raises concerns about the long-term integrity of root canal-treated teeth and highlights the need for further investigation into the effect of different NiTi systems on dentinal damage.⁹

By using a stereo microscope, researchers can accurately assess micro-apical cracks after root canal preparation, providing valuable insights into the effectiveness of different preparation techniques and instrumentation.¹⁰

To the best of knowledge, no published research investigated the apical cracks in the root canal walls during root canal preparation, obturation and retreatment using either rotating or reciprocating rotary systems. Our null hypothesis was that would be no statistically significant difference between rotating or reciprocating rotary systems during root canal preparation, filling, and retreatment in producing apical cracks within the root canal walls.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram representing distribution of samples through groups and subgroups.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Size Calculation & Selection

G* power statistical analysis software was used to determine sufficient sample size.¹¹ The sample size was determined on a sample population of 40 single straight rooted human teeth with an α error probability of 0.05, effect size f of 0.25, and a 0.97 power (1- β). The teeth used in this study were freshly extracted for periodontal, prosthodontic, or orthodontic reasons. Selection criteria included having a completely formed apex, absence of root caries, and no internal or external resorption to prevent structural loss during transverse sectioning. Only teeth that had not undergone prior endodontic treatment were included to ensure standardized instrumentation and obturation. Additionally, samples with visible cracks were excluded to prevent fracture during sectioning, and those with anatomical abnormalities, such as fusion or dilacerations, were not considered.

Maxillary canines were immersed in 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (Clorox; Household Cleaning Products of Egypt, Cairo, Egypt) for one hour for disinfection. The remaining external tissue fragments and calculus were removed from the external surface of teeth by scaling, and then they were washed and stored in distilled water at room temperature till time of use. Bucco-lingual and mesio-distal radiographs were taken to confirm the presence of a single canal.

2.2. Samples Preparation and Classification

Crowns of the collected teeth were decapitated at a standard length of 16-mm from the apical root end using tapered stone (Mani Inc., Japan) at high speed with water coolant for exposing orifice with a direct access to the root canal. One millimeter from the apex of each tooth was ground perpendicular to the long axis of the tooth using Isomet 4000 microsaw (Buehler, USA) with a diamond disc 0.6 mm thickness at speed 2500 rpm and feeding rate 10 mm/min under water cooling and the apical surface was polished. Patency to the canal was negotiated using #10 K-file (Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) to its full length and passed 1 mm beyond the apex. The working length for root canal preparation was set 1-mm shorter than the apical foramen.⁹

A standard model for periodontal ligament simulation was made. Teeth were placed in melted wax up to 1 mm below the cervical end. After cooling, the teeth were being embedded in blocks filled with gypsum.¹⁰ After setting, teeth were removed and the wax was cleaned from the root surface and "sockets" using warm water.¹² The "sockets" were then filled with a polyether impression material Impregum (3MESPE, St. Paul, MN, USA) using a molding syringe. Teeth were reinserted into the respective "sockets". The excess impression material was removed with a

scalpel. The samples were classified into two main groups ($n=20$) according to the instrumentation technique used during chemo mechanical preparation (Fig.1).

2.3. Root Canal Preparation

2.3.1. Group A – Revo-S System (Continuous Rotation)

In this group, root canals were prepared using the Revo-S rotary system in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines, employing continuous rotation. The procedure began with initial canal negotiation using a stainless steel K-file (#10, 21 mm) to gain preliminary tactile feedback regarding the canal's curvature and anatomy, complementing radiographic findings. Instruments were frequently withdrawn and cleaned with alcohol-soaked gauze to prevent dentin debris accumulation.

For shaping, Revo-S files were operated with the X-Smart IQ endodontic motor (Dentsply GmbH, Bensheim, Germany) at speeds ranging from 250 to 400 rpm. The SC1 instrument was advanced apically with a gentle, pressure-free, passive movement. SC2 was employed using a dynamic three-wave technique (repeated upward and downward motions), while the SU file was similarly advanced in a slow, pressureless, apical progression.¹³ Apical patency was maintained between each file insertion using a small hand file.

Irrigation was performed with 5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), delivered via a 27-gauge syringe needle, with a total of 10 mL used per canal. A chelating agent (MD; Meta Biomed Co., Ltd., Korea) was applied as a lubricant and to aid in debris removal. Final apical shaping was achieved with the SU file, expanding the apical portion to a 6% taper, in continuity with prior preparations.

2.3.2. Group B – WaveOne System (Reciprocating Motion)

Samples in this group were instrumented using the WaveOne file system, following the manufacturer's protocol involving reciprocating motion. Initial canal exploration was performed using a conventional stainless steel K-file (#10, 21 mm) to assess the internal canal anatomy in conjunction with pre-operative radiographs. Instruments were regularly withdrawn and wiped with gauze moistened with alcohol to remove dentinal debris.

The WaveOne Primary file, with a tip size of ISO 25 and a variable taper that begins with 8% apically and decreases coronally, was used to prepare the canals to the full working length. Throughout the procedure, canals were irrigated with 5% NaOCl using a 27-gauge syringe needle. A total volume of 10 mL of irrigant was used per canal. MD chelating agent was utilized to facilitate lubrication and enhance removal of smear layer and debris.

2.4. Root Canal Obturation

All specimens underwent obturation using gutta-percha cones (Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) in conjunction with an epoxy resin-based sealer, AH Plus (Dentsply DeTrey, Konstanz, Germany), following the cold lateral compaction technique. The master cone was fitted to the full working length, after which a size 30, 2% taper finger spreader (Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland) was inserted parallel to the master cone, stopping 1 mm short of the working length. The spreader was maintained in position for approximately 10 to 60 seconds before being withdrawn, allowing the subsequent placement of accessory gutta-percha cones to ensure lateral compaction.

Following obturation, the coronal portion of each canal was sealed using a temporary restorative material, Cavit (Dentsply, Maillefer, Ballaigues, Switzerland). All samples were then stored in an environment of 100% humidity at 37°C for a period of two weeks to allow for sealer setting and material stabilization.

2.5. Root Canal Retreatment Procedure

Each experimental group was further divided into two subgroups (n = 10) based on the instrumentation method employed during the retreatment phase.

2.5.1. Subgroup 1 – R-Endo System (Continuous Rotation)

In this subgroup, removal of root canal filling materials was carried out using the R-Endo file system (Micro-Mega, Besançon, France), following the manufacturer's recommended continuous rotation protocol. Instrumentation was performed at a rotational speed of 300 to 400 rpm using a torque-controlled electric motor.

The procedure began with the Endo Flare file, which was used to eliminate gutta-percha material from the canal orifice to approximately 3 mm apically. Sequentially, the R1 file was used to clean the coronal third, R2 for the middle third, and R3 for the apical third of the canal. Throughout the process, 5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) was used as the irrigant, delivered via a 27-gauge syringe needle, with a total volume of 10 mL per canal.

2.5.2. Subgroup 2 – WaveOne System (Reciprocating Motion)

In this subgroup, canal fillings were removed using the WaveOne system in reciprocal motion, in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines. For larger canals, the WaveOne Large file (ISO size 40, taper 8% decreasing coronally) was utilized. Irrigation was similarly performed using 5% NaOCl (10 mL per canal), administered with a 27-gauge needle.

2.5.3. Common Protocol for All Subgroups

Retreatment was considered complete when the instruments no longer carried visible remnants of gutta-percha or sealer, and canal walls appeared smooth upon inspection. Radiographic imaging was employed to confirm the thorough removal of filling materials. A torque- and speed-regulated endodontic motor was used for all instrumentation steps.

Each file was used to treat a single canal only. Additionally, sterile distilled water (5 mL) was used to irrigate the canal after every three pecking motions, using a 27-gauge needle attached to a disposable plastic syringe. The needle tip was passively inserted to a depth 1 mm short of the working length and was never forced into the canal wall during irrigation to ensure safety and efficacy.

2.6. Detection and Evaluation of Apical Cracks

All specimens (n = 40) were carefully extracted from their simulated alveolar sockets and thoroughly rinsed under running water. Apical root surfaces were examined using a digital stereomicroscope (Guangdong, China) at 80× magnification. Each sample was evaluated at four distinct stages of the endodontic

procedure: prior to instrumentation, after canal preparation, following obturation, and after the retreatment phase. Digital images were captured using image analysis software (Scope Capture 1.1.1.1 Ltd. Co.) to facilitate documentation and crack assessment.

The primary aim was to detect the presence or absence of apical cracks. High-resolution images of the apical root surfaces were recorded and inspected for structural defects.¹⁵ The evaluation focused on the apical third of the root, specifically at a horizontal cross-section located 1 mm from the apex, using the same digital stereomicroscope (80×10 magnification).

To ensure objectivity, all assessments were conducted in a blinded fashion by two independent examiners who were unaware of the procedural details or the study's purpose. Each sample was evaluated twice to confirm intra-examiner reliability.

The following classification system was applied^{12,16}:

Score 0 – No Crack: Specimens showed intact root dentin with no visible cracks or craze lines on either the internal canal wall or the external root surface.

Score 1 – Crack Present: A crack was identified as any visible line extending either from the canal lumen toward the dentin or from the external root surface inward.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

All data were collected from digital images results analysis, tabulated, and statistically analyzed. The mean and standard deviation values were calculated for each group. Data were explored for normality using Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests, data showed non-parametric (not normal) distribution. Chi-square test was used to compare between two groups in non-related samples. Friedman test was used to compare between more than two groups in related samples. Wilcoxon test was used to compare between two groups in related samples. The significance level was set at $P \leq 0.05$. Statistical analysis was performed with IBM® SPSS® Statistics Version 20 for Windows.

3. Results

The mean apical crack scores across all groups significantly increased from baseline (before preparation) through each subsequent treatment step, indicating progressive dentinal damage during root canal procedures ($p < 0.05$). Specifically, significant within-group differences were noted for both main groups and their respective subgroups from baseline to after retreatment ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, substantial differences were observed when comparing all subgroups collectively ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1).

Group B, particularly subgroup 2 (Wave One preparation and

Table 1. The mean ± standard deviation (SD) and P values of apical crack score of all groups during different root canal steps.

Groups	Treatment Steps	Mean ± SD	Median	Within each group	Within each subgroup	Within all subgroups
Group A and subgroup 1	Before Preparation	0.00±0.00	0	0.015*	<0.001*	<0.001*
Group A and subgroup 1	After Preparation	0.30±0.48	0			
Group A and subgroup 1	After Obturation	0.40±0.52	0			
Group A and subgroup 1	After Retreatment	0.50±0.53	0.5			
Group B and subgroup 1	Before Preparation	0.00±0.00	0	0.004*		
Group B and subgroup 1	After Preparation	0.40±0.52	0			
Group B and subgroup 1	After Obturation	0.50±0.53	0.5			
Group B and subgroup 1	After Retreatment	0.60±0.52	1			
Group A and subgroup 2	Before Preparation	0.00±0.00	0	0.017*	<0.001*	
Group A and subgroup 2	After Preparation	0.30±0.48	0			
Group A and subgroup 2	After Obturation	0.30±0.48	0			
Group A and subgroup 2	After Retreatment	0.50±0.53	0.5			
Group B and subgroup 2	Before Preparation	0.00±0.00	0	0.001*		
Group B and subgroup 2	After Preparation	0.60±0.52	1			
Group B and subgroup 2	After Obturation	0.60±0.52	1			
Group B and subgroup 2	After Retreatment	0.70±0.48	1			

Friedman Analysis, Group A: Treatment with Revo S, Group B: Treatment with Wave One, Subgroup 1: Retreatment with R Endo, Subgroup 2: Retreatment with Wave one

Table 2. Comparison of apical crack scores between different groups.

Comparison	Comparison	Treatment Steps	P-value
Group A and Subgroup 1	Group B and Subgroup 1	Before Preparation	1.000
Group A and Subgroup 1	Group B and Subgroup 1	After Preparation	0.648
Group A and Subgroup 1	Group B and Subgroup 1	After Obturation	0.661
Group A and Subgroup 1	Group B and Subgroup 1	After Retreatment	0.661
Group A and Subgroup 2	Group B and Subgroup 2	Before Preparation	1.000
Group A and Subgroup 2	Group B and Subgroup 2	After Preparation	0.189
Group A and Subgroup 2	Group B and Subgroup 2	After Obturation	0.189
Group A and Subgroup 2	Group B and Subgroup 2	After Retreatment	0.374
Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	Before Preparation	1.000
Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	After Preparation	0.602
Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	After Obturation	1.000
Subgroup 1	Subgroup 2	After Retreatment	0.752

Wilcoxon Rank test, Group A: Treatment with Revo S, Group B: Treatment with Wave One, Subgroup 1: Retreatment with R Endo, Subgroup 2: Retreatment with Wave one

crack scores, culminating at 0.70 ± 0.48 post-retreatment, whereas Group A exhibited comparatively lower scores at corresponding treatment stages (Table 1).

The comparison of apical crack scores between groups revealed no statistically significant differences at any treatment step. Specifically, when Group A (Revo S) and Group B (Wave One) were compared within Subgroup 1 (R-Endo retreatment) or Subgroup 2 (Wave One retreatment), no significant differences were detected before preparation, after preparation, obturation, or retreatment ($p > 0.05$). Additionally, comparisons between Subgroup 1 and Subgroup 2, irrespective of preparation instruments, also showed no significant differences at any treatment phase ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2).

After the preparation phase, cracks were observed in 30% of samples treated with Revo S (Group A) and 50% of samples treated with Wave One (Group B). However, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.202$). Despite a higher frequency of crack formation in the Wave One group, the observed differences between the two treatment methods did not reach statistical significance (Table 3).

Representative images of apical cracks formed during root canal preparation and retreatment procedures using continuous

rotation (Revo-S, R-Endo) and reciprocating motion (Wave One) are presented in Fig. 2

4. Discussion

One of the fundamental objectives of chemo-mechanical root canal preparation is the thorough elimination of microorganisms, necrotic pulp tissue, and debris, while simultaneously shaping the canal to accommodate obturation materials.¹⁷ However, overly aggressive instrumentation can compromise the integrity of root dentin, potentially inducing dentinal defects such as microcracks, fissures, or vertical root fractures—conditions that may contribute to long-term treatment failure.¹⁸ These adverse events are often linked to factors such as the instrument's design features, including its cross-sectional shape, size, taper, and the physical properties of the alloy from which it is manufactured.¹⁹

This study utilized maxillary canines with single, straight roots containing one root canal to minimize anatomical variability. Teeth exhibiting deviations in the position of the major apical foramen relative to the canal axis were excluded to prevent potential confounding factors in crack formation and to enhance standardization. To further control variables and facilitate

Fig. 2. (A) Apical crack after root canal preparation using continuous rotation motion (Revo-S). (B) Apical crack after root canal preparation using reciprocating motion (Wave One). (C) Apical crack after root canal retreatment using continuous rotation motion (R-Endo). (D) Apical crack after root canal retreatment using reciprocating motion (Wave One). Arrows indicate the presence of visible cracks.

Table 3. The frequencies of cracks in main 2 groups (After preparation).

Group	Crack status	n	%	p-value
Group A (treated by Revo S)	No cracks	14	70%	0.202
	Cracks	6	30%	
Group B (treated by Wave One)	No cracks	10	50%	
	Cracks	10	50%	

consistent evaluation, the apical 1 mm of each root was sectioned. This decision was based on the frequent occurrence of periapical pathology that can compromise the anatomical apex and apical constriction. Additionally, the presence of apical delta ramifications in the terminal 1 mm of the root can resemble cracks, potentially confounding microscopic analysis. Trimming the apex also created a flat surface, which improved the clarity of crack detection and allowed accurate monitoring of crack initiation and propagation under stereomicroscopic observation throughout the procedures.²⁰

While it is acknowledged that sectioning of root apices may theoretically introduce structural damage or initiate crack formation, the findings of the present study do not support this concern. No cracks were identified in either Group A or Group B during the pre-treatment evaluation phase. This observation aligns with previous research, which similarly reported an absence of crack formation following root sectioning procedures.²⁰

Apical cracks were examined using a digital stereomicroscope at 80× magnification. All images were assessed independently by two blinded evaluators. In instances where discrepancies arose between the observers, the samples were reanalyzed jointly until a consensus was reached.^{16,21}

In this study, the null hypothesis was supported, as no statistically significant difference was found between Group A (rotational motion) and Group B (reciprocating motion) with respect to apical crack formation during root canal preparation. These findings are consistent with those reported by Yoldaş et al.²², who also observed no significant differences between experimental groups. Their investigation noted the presence of apical cracks in 25% of specimens prepared with the Revo-S system, a proportion comparable to that observed in the current study. They proposed that the design of endodontic instruments plays a critical role in concentrating stress and strain at the apical third, thereby increasing the likelihood of dentinal defects and canal deviations. Such structural compromises can act as precursors to vertical root fractures, particularly following obturation and coronal restoration, which may further propagate pre-existing cracks.

In the present study, the lowest incidence of defects was recorded in Group A, instrumented with the Revo-S system. Although no prior studies specifically addressing the performance of this file system in crack formation were found in the literature, the manufacturer claims that the Revo-S file induces less stress on dentin. This is attributed to its asymmetrical cross-sectional design and extended coronal cutting portion, which collectively enhance flexibility and reduce dentinal strain during instrumentation.

Moreover, the WaveOne system, being a single-file technique, necessitates repeated entry into the root canal using the same instrument to achieve the full working length. This repeated engagement may contribute to increased mechanical stress on the canal walls, potentially resulting in a higher incidence of crack formation compared to the Revo-S system.

The findings of the present study are consistent with those reported by Bruklien et al.²³, who also observed no statistically significant difference between the experimental groups. In their investigation, apical cracks were identified in 55% of the samples instrumented with the WaveOne system—a percentage that closely aligns with the outcomes of our study. The variation in the incidence of dentinal defects between the Revo-S and WaveOne systems may be attributed to differences in their mechanical action and instrument geometry. Specifically, the WaveOne file features a triangular or modified triangular cross-sectional design, which

may limit its cutting efficiency and reduce chip space. These characteristics can lead to increased stress accumulation at the apical third, thereby elevating the risk of crack formation.

Conversely, some studies have reported conflicting results regarding the impact of continuous rotational versus reciprocating motion on dentinal crack formation. Liu et al.²⁴ demonstrated that reciprocating systems, such as Reciproc files, induced fewer dentinal cracks compared to continuous rotation systems like ProTaper. In their study, continuous rotation instruments—OneShape and ProTaper—resulted in apical cracks in 35% and 50% of samples, respectively, whereas the Reciproc system, operating in a reciprocating motion akin to the balanced force technique, produced cracks in only 5% of specimens. The authors suggested that reciprocating motion may reduce torsional and flexural stresses, limit canal transportation, and offer enhanced resistance to cyclic fatigue. Although variations in cross-sectional design were noted, the reduced incidence of dentinal damage observed with reciprocating systems could be attributed, at least in part, to the kinematics of the instrumentation technique.²⁵

In contrast to the findings of the present study, Kansal et al.²⁰ reported a lower incidence of dentinal defects when using instruments with reciprocating motion compared to those utilizing continuous rotation. Their results indicated that both the WaveOne file and the single F2 ProTaper file, when operated in reciprocating motion, produced significantly fewer cracks than the conventional ProTaper system in continuous rotation. The authors attributed this to the fact that continuous rotation tends to generate concentrated stress along the canal walls, increasing the likelihood of crack initiation. In contrast, reciprocating systems maintain better centering within the canal and, through alternating clockwise and counterclockwise movements, allow the file to disengage periodically when it binds to the canal walls during instrumentation. This motion not only facilitates smoother shaping but also reduces both flexural and torsional stresses by minimizing the time the cutting blades remain in contact with dentin, thereby lowering the risk of crack formation.

Several studies concluded that continuous rotational systems were associated with a higher incidence of dentinal crack formation compared to reciprocating systems.²⁶⁻²⁸ Their findings suggested that the continuous application of rotational force and consistent torque by NiTi rotary instruments can exert substantial mechanical stress on the canal walls, thereby increasing the likelihood of crack development. In contrast, the reciprocating motion of WaveOne was reported to facilitate intermittent stress release, allowing the instrument to disengage before advancing further into the canal, which may help reduce the incidence of dentinal damage.

In further contrast to the findings of the present study, De-Deus et al.²⁹ found no causal relationship between dentinal crack formation and the biomechanical preparation of root canals using Reciproc, WaveOne, or BioRace systems. Their micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) based investigation revealed that all dentinal defects observed in the postoperative scans were already present in the corresponding preoperative images, indicating that no new cracks were induced as a result of the instrumentation procedures. The study employed high-resolution micro-computed tomography to assess dentinal integrity before and after canal enlargement using both rotary and reciprocating systems, providing a nondestructive and reliable method for defect detection.

In the present study, no statistically significant difference in dentinal crack formation was observed during the obturation phase. However, Shemesh et al.³⁰ reported a higher incidence of dentinal defects following root canal filling using the lateral compaction technique compared to the passive compaction approach. This discrepancy may be explained by methodological differences, particularly in the application of the spreader. In the current study, careful and controlled use of the spreader likely minimized the wedging effect—a known mechanical stressor

implicated in crack initiation during lateral compaction—thereby reducing the potential for crack formation during obturation.

The lack of a significant difference between the R-Endo and WaveOne systems during retreatment in the present study aligns with findings by Citak et al.³¹, who also reported no statistically significant differences among various NiTi systems. They concluded that crack formation was unrelated to file design or motion type but rather linked to mechanical stress during filling material removal. Other studies^{30,32} similarly attributed crack occurrence during retreatment to the additional stress imposed by repeated instrumentation.

This study presents several limitations that warrant consideration. Firstly, as an in vitro investigation, it cannot fully replicate the complexity of clinical conditions, where factors such as masticatory forces, the biomechanical function of the periodontal ligament, and biological responses may significantly influence the development and progression of dentinal cracks. Although efforts were made to simulate intraoral conditions by maintaining humidity, the absence of physiological dynamics limits the extrapolation of the results to clinical practice.

Secondly, the sample size was relatively limited (n = 40), and only single-rooted teeth were included. This restricts the generalizability of the findings to multi-rooted teeth or those with more complex anatomical variations. Another important limitation involves the methodology used for crack detection. The stereomicroscopic examination of sectioned samples, while widely employed, may introduce or exacerbate dentinal defects, thereby confounding the accuracy of the observations.

The use of more advanced, non-invasive imaging techniques—such as micro-CT, optical coherence tomography, or infrared tomography—could have enabled a more precise and artifact-free evaluation of dentinal integrity. Additionally, the scope of the current study was limited to immediate crack formation following canal preparation, obturation, and retreatment. The potential for crack propagation over time, under the influence of functional occlusal loads or restorative procedures, remains unaddressed. Future investigations should consider longitudinal in vivo studies and clinical trials to evaluate the long-term effects of endodontic procedures on root structural integrity under realistic clinical conditions.

5. Conclusion

Within the limitations of this study, both continuous rotation and reciprocating NiTi systems were found to induce apical cracks during root canal preparation and retreatment. However, no statistically significant difference was observed between the two kinematic motions in terms of crack formation. These findings suggest that both techniques can be used without a notable difference in dentinal integrity.

References

- Gergi RM, Osta NE, Naaman AS. Dentinal crack formation during root canal preparations by the Twisted File Adaptive, Reciproc and WaveOne instruments. *Eur J Dent*. 2015;9:508–511.
- Çapar İD, Uysal B, Ok E, Arslan H. Effect of the size of the apical enlargement with rotary instruments, single-cone filling, post space preparation with drills, fiber post removal, and root canal filling removal on apical crack initiation and propagation. *J Endod*. 2015;41:253–256.
- Wilcox LR., Roskelley C., Sutton T. The relationship of root canal enlargement to finger-spreader induced vertical root fracture. *J Endod*. 1997;23:533–534.
- Gündoğar M, Sezgin GP. Cyclic fatigue resistance of Genius, RC Gold, and Revo-S nickel-titanium instruments. *Int J Appl Dent Sci*. 2018;4:342–345.
- Aggarwal A, Nawal RR, Yadav S, Talwar S, Kunnoth S, Mahajan P. Comparative evaluation of dentinal microcrack formation before and after root canal preparation using rotary, reciprocating, and adaptive instruments at different working lengths—a micro-computed tomographic study. *J Endod*. 2021;47:1314–1320.
- Akpınar KE, Altunbaş D, Kuştarıcı A. The efficacy of two rotary NiTi instruments and H-files to remove gutta-percha from root canals. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal*. 2012;17:e506–511.
- Jayasenthil A, Sathish ES, Prakash P. Evaluation of manual and two-rotary NiTi retreatment systems in removing gutta-percha obturated with two root canal sealers. *ISRN Dent*. 2012;2012:10.
- Amaral PG., dos Santos RL, Salazar-Silva JR, Batista AU, Bonan PR. Prevalence of dentinal defects after root canal preparations in molars with Reciproc and WaveOne systems. *Pesqui Bras Odontopediatria Clin Integ*. 2016;16:159–165.
- Pawar AM, Thakur B, Kfir A, Kim HC. Dentinal defects induced by six different endodontic files when used for oval root canals: an in vitro comparative study. *Restor Dent Endod*. 2019;44:e31.
- Soni D, Raisingani D, Mathur R, Madan N, Visnoi S. Incidence of apical crack initiation during canal preparation using hand stainless steel (K-file) and hand NiTi (ProTaper) files. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2016;9:303–309.
- Faul F, Erdfelder E, Lang AG, Buchner A. G*Power 3. A flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behav Res Methods*. 2007;39:175–191.
- Milani AS, Froughreyhani M, Rahimi S, Jafarabadi MA, Paksefat S. The effect of root canal preparation on the development of dentin cracks. *Iran Endod J*. 2012;7:177–182.
- Basrani B, Roth K, Sas G, Kishen A, Peters OA. Torsional profiles of new and used Revo-S rotary instruments: an in vitro study. *J Endod*. 2011;37:982–992.
- Mittal R, Singla MG, Garg A, Dhawan A. A comparison of apical bacterial extrusion in manual, ProTaper rotary, and One Shape rotary instrumentation techniques. *J Endod*. 2015;41:2040–2044.
- Topçuoğlu HS, Düzgün S, Kesim B, Tuncay O. Incidence of apical crack initiation and propagation during the removal of root canal filling material with ProTaper and Mtwo rotary nickel-titanium retreatment instruments and hand files. *J Endod*. 2014;40:1009–1012.
- Mathew R, Shetty S, Shetty H. Influence of speed on microcracks in root dentin during root canal preparation with two rotary system ProTaper Universal and Revo-S. *Int J Adv Res*. 2017;5:1889–1894.
- Goldman M, White RR, Moser CR, Tenca JI. A comparison of three methods of cleaning and shaping the root canal in vitro. *J Endod*. 1988;14:7–12.
- Peters OA. Current challenges and concepts in the preparation of root canal systems. a review. *J Endod*. 2004;30:559–567.
- Bergmans L, Van Cleynenbreugel J, Beullens M, Wevers M, Van Meerbeek B, Lambrechts P. Smooth flexible versus active tapered shaft design using NiTi rotary instruments. *Int Endod J*. 2002;35:820–828.
- Kansal R, Rajput A, Talwar S, Roongta R, Verma M. Assessment of dentinal damage during canal preparation using reciprocating and rotary files. *J Endod*. 2014;40:1443–1446.
- Shemesh H, Bier CA, Wu MK, Tanomaru-Filho M, Wesselink PR. The effects of canal preparation and filling on the incidence of dentinal defects. *Int Endod J*. 2009;42:208–213.

22. Yoldaş O, Yılmaz S, Atakan G, Kuden C, Kaşan Z. Dentinal microcrack formation during root canal preparations by different NiTi rotary instruments and the self-adjusting file. *J Endod.* 2012;38:232–235.
23. Bürklein S, Tsotsis P, Schäfer E. Incidence of dentinal defects after root canal preparation: reciprocating versus rotary instrumentation. *J Endod.* 2013;39:501–4.
24. Liu R, Hou BX, Wesselink PR, Wu MK, Shemesh H. The incidence of root microcracks caused by 3 different single-file systems versus the ProTaper system. *J Endod.* 2013;39:1054-1056.
25. Jalali S, Eftekhari B, Paymanpour P, Yazdizadeh M, Jafarzadeh M. Effects of Reciproc, Mtwo and ProTaper instruments on formation of rootfracture. *Iran Endod J.* 2015;10:252-256.
26. Ashwinkumar V, Krithikadatta J, Surendran S, Velmurugan N. Effect of reciprocating file motion on microcrack formation in root canals: an SEM study. *Int Endod J.* 2014 ;47:622-627.
27. Aishwarya S, Rahul M. Effect of continuous and reciprocating file motion on microcrack formation in root canals during retreatment: A SEM Study. *Acta Sci Dent Sci.* 2021;6:44-50.
28. Aarthi S, Sivakumar JS, Sivakumar AA, Soundappan JS, Chittrarasu M, Jayanthi G. Comparative evaluation of incidence of dentinal defects after root canal preparation using three different endodontic retreatment systems - An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent Endod.* 2024;27:262-267.
29. De-Deus G, Silva EJNL, Marins J, Souza E, Neves AA, Gonc F, Belladonna A, et al. Lack of Causal Relationship between Dentinal Microcracks and Root Canal Preparation with Reciprocation Systems. *J Endod.* 2014;40:1447–1450.
30. Shemesh H, Roeleveld AC, Wesselink PR, Wu MK. Damage to root dentin during retreatment procedures. *J Endod.* 2011;37:63-66.
31. Cıtaç M, Ozyurek T. Effect of different nickel-titanium rotary files on dentinal crack formation during retreatment procedure. *J Dent Res Dent Clin Dent Prosp.* 2017;11:90-97.
32. Topcuoglu HS, Demirbuga S, Tuncay O, Pala K, Arslan H, Karatas E. The Effects of Mtwo, R-Endo, and D-RaCe Retreatment Instruments on the Incidence of Dentinal Defects during the Removal of Root Canal Filling Material. *J Endod.* 2014;40:266-270.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest is available

Original Article

Comparison of the Shear Bond Strengths of Two Different Restorative Materials to Biodentine and BIOfactor MTA

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Biodentine exhibited significantly higher shear bond strength to both flowable composite and glass ionomer cement. Notably, the Biodentine-flowable composite combination yielded the most favorable results.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: The aim of this study was to compare the shear bond strengths of glass ionomer cement and flowable composite to the calcium silicate-based materials- Biodentine and BIOfactor MTA.

Materials and Methods: Biodentine and BIOfactor MTA were prepared and placed in teflon molds with a diameter of 8 mm and a height of 2 mm. Material discs were incubated at 37°C and 100% humidity for 24h. Material samples were embedded in acrylic blocks. Flowable composite (Ruby Flow, Ruby Dent, Incidental, England, Türkiye) or glass ionomer cement Nova Glass F, Imicryl, Konya, Türkiye) with 3-mm diameter and 2-mm height was applied on the calcium silicate based cements. Samples were incubated under the same conditions for 24 hours. Samples were subjected to the shear test method using a universal test machine with the loading speed of 1 mm/min. The peak force was recorded when bond failure occurred. Statistical analysis was carried out using Kruskal Wallis and Mann-Whitney U tests.

Results: A significant difference was found between the shear bond strength of BIOfactor MTA-flowable composite and Biodentine-flowable composite groups ($p < 0.05$). There was a significant difference between BIOfactor MTA-glass ionomer cement and Biodentine glass ionomer cement groups ($p < 0.05$). Biodentine showed higher bond strength to both materials. Both Biodentine and BIOfactor MTA showed higher shear bond strength with the flowable composite than glass ionomer cement.

Conclusion: Biodentine has higher shear bond strength to restorative materials than BIOfactor MTA. Both calcium silicate-based cements have higher shear bond strength to flowable composite.

1. Introduction

Vital pulp therapies include procedures such as indirect pulp capping, direct pulp capping, partial pulpotomy, and total pulpotomy. Calcium hydroxide-based materials have long been considered the gold standard in endodontics and have been used in many treatments, including vital pulp therapies. However, calcium hydroxide has disadvantages such as not setting as quickly as mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA), dissolving over time, causing microleakage, and requiring prolonged presence in the environment to be effective.¹

Bioceramics or bioactive endodontic cements are biocompatible cements containing compounds such as tricalcium silicate, dicalcium silicate, tricalcium aluminate, calcium sulfate dihydrate, bismuth oxide, calcium oxide, aluminum oxide, and many similar components.² MTA and other bioceramics have a wide range of clinical applications and have been used with successful clinical outcomes in vital pulp therapy, root resorptions, perforation repair, root-end filling in apical surgery, apexification and regenerative endodontic procedures.^{1,3} The main advantages of bioceramics are their high biocompatibility, excellent sealing ability, and ability to set in the presence of moisture.⁴ Their disadvantages include long setting time, potential wash-out when exposed to oral fluids, tooth discoloration, difficulty in application, and high cost.^{5,6} In addition, once set, they are difficult to remove, and there is no known solvent for them.⁷

Biodentine, an important prototype of bioceramics, is a fast-setting, easy-to-use bioceramic material. It is prepared by adding liquid to the powder contained in a capsule and then agitating it in a mixer to achieve a cement-like consistency.⁸ Biodentine offers advantages such as superior physical and biologic properties.⁹

A recently introduced material, BIOfactor MTA (Imicryl Dental, Konya, Türkiye), has similar indications to other bioceramic materials. It can be prepared in either high or low viscosity depending on the type of treatment. Recent studies have investigated the bond strength of BIOfactor MTA to root dentin. Akbulut et al.¹⁰ reported that the push-out bond strength of BIOfactor MTA was comparable to that of MTA-Angelus and Biodentine in permanent teeth, with all materials showing similar resistance to dislodgement forces. In another study focusing on primary teeth, Özer et al.¹¹ found that BIOfactor MTA demonstrated significantly higher bond strength to root canal dentin compared to calcium hydroxide-based sealers, suggesting its potential as a durable alternative in pediatric endodontics.

Bioceramics are applied directly over the exposed pulp tissue during vital pulp therapies. Their use in regenerative procedures involves controlling infection, disinfecting the root canal, inducing bleeding, and then applying a barrier material.^{12,13} In both cases, it is recommended to place a restorative material such as glass ionomer cement (GIC), resin modified glass ionomer cement (RMGIC), or flowable composite over the bioceramic material, followed by a final restoration using either composite or amalgam.^{14,15}

Although the main focus in teeth undergoing vital pulp therapy or regenerative endodontic treatment is pulp health and tooth vitality, all restorative materials used in the oral cavity are exposed to chewing forces of varying direction and magnitude. Dentin and bioceramic/restorative materials bond together through adhesive forces. Furthermore, calcium silicate-based materials and the restorative materials applied over them are exposed to intraoral

Fig. 1. BIOfactor MTA (A) and Biodentine (B) specimens prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions for placement into molds for the study

masticatory forces; therefore, their shear bond strength is a critical clinical success parameter. The strength of the adhesive bond between materials used in endodontic procedures also affects marginal adaptation and microleakage. This in vitro study aimed to evaluate and compare the shear bond strength of Biodentine and a newly developed calcium silicate-based material, BIOfactor MTA, to flowable composite resin or conventional GIC applied over them as restorative materials.

2. Materials and Methods

The calcium silicate-based materials Biodentine (Septodont, Saint-Maur-des-Fossés, France) and BIOfactor MTA (Imicryl Dental, Konya, Türkiye) were tested in this study. All materials were prepared according to the manufacturers' instructions to ensure standardization and optimal handling properties. BIOfactor MTA was prepared by mixing 1 scope of powder with 1 drop of liquid on a glass slab. Biodentine was prepared by adding 5 drops of liquid into one capsule of powder and mixing it for 30 seconds in a mixer (Fig. 1).

The mixed materials were transferred into Teflon molds measuring 8 mm in diameter and 2 mm in height, forming cylindrical material discs ($n = 30$). The prepared material samples were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C in 100% humidity. After removal from the incubator (Nüve, Ankara, Türkiye), the samples were embedded in the center of autopolymerizing acrylic resin blocks (BG Dental, Integra, Ankara, Türkiye). To obtain identical surfaces, the specimens were polished under distilled water for 30 seconds.

The specimens were randomly assigned to two restorative material subgroups ($n = 15$ each): one receiving a flowable composite (Nova Compo HF, Imicryl Dental, Konya, Türkiye) and the other GIC (Nova Glass F, Imicryl Dental, Konya, Türkiye). This resulted in four experimental groups of 15 samples each (Fig. 2):

- Group 1A: BIOfactor MTA with Flowable Composite
- Group 1B: BIOfactor MTA with GIC
- Group 2A: Biodentine with Flowable Composite
- Group 2B: Biodentine with GIC

A Teflon mold with an inner cavity of 3 mm in diameter and 2 mm in height was placed on top and at the center of the BIOfactor MTA and Biodentine material discs. The mold was filled with either a flowable composite or GIC. For the flowable composite specimens, the surfaces of the BIOfactor MTA or Biodentine were first etched with acid (RubyEtch, Incidental, İstanbul, Türkiye) for 30 seconds, rinsed for 15 seconds to remove acid residues, and then air-dried. A universal adhesive (Nova Compo B Plus, Imicryl Dental, Konya, Türkiye) was then applied to the surface using an applicator for 20 seconds and gently air-thinned. The adhesive was polymerized using a light-curing unit (Woodpecker Medical Instruments, Guilin, China) for 20 seconds. The flowable composite

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the materials used and the experimental groups in the study.

was applied into the mold and polymerized using the same light-curing device for another 20 seconds.

For the GIC, the material was mixed using a cement spatula at a 3:1 powder-to-liquid ratio for approximately 35 seconds and applied into the Teflon mold. The mold was removed either immediately after flowable composite polymerization or 15 minutes after the application of the GIC.

The specimens prepared in this way were incubated again at 37°C and 100% humidity for 24 hours. Then, the samples were placed in a universal testing machine (Besmak, Ankara, Türkiye). A sloped loading head was used to apply force perpendicularly to the calcium silicate cement–restorative material interface and the surface at a constant speed of 1 mm/min until failure occurred (Fig. 3). The maximum force at the point of failure was recorded in Newtons and then converted into megapascals ($1 \text{ MPa} = 1 \text{ N/mm}^2$).¹⁶

To evaluate the failure types (adhesive, cohesive, or mixed) in each group, the surfaces of the BIOfactor MTA and Biodentine specimens were examined under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SZ61, Tokyo, Japan) at 12× magnification and the failures were categorized as follows:

Adhesive Failure: Bond failure occurring at the interface between BIOfactor MTA/Biodentine and the restorative material.

Cohesive Failure: Bond failure occurring within the structure of the BIOfactor MTA, Biodentine, or restorative material.

Mixed Failure: A combination of adhesive and cohesive failure.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses in this study were performed using the SPSS 23.0 software package. The normality of the data distribution was first assessed using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The p-values obtained from the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test were found to be less than 0.05, indicating that the data did not follow a normal

Fig. 3. Schematic illustration showing the experimental setup including all components of the study and the direction of the applied force.

Table 1. Comparison of Shear Bond Strength Values (MPa) Between Materials

Materials	Flowable Composite	GIC	P-value
BIOfactor MTA	5.89±0.50	2.86±0.20	0.001*
Biodentine	7.98±1.13	3.05±0.24	0.001*
P-value	0.001*	0.028*	

distribution. Therefore, non-parametric statistical tests were deemed appropriate for data analysis. To compare the Newton and MPa values between the different material groups, the Mann-Whitney U test was used for pairwise comparisons. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

The mean shear bond strength values for each material are presented in Table 1. The highest shear bond strength was observed in the Biodentine – flowable composite group (7.98 ± 1.13), while the lowest value was recorded in the BIOfactor MTA – GIC group (2.86 ± 0.20).

A statistically significant difference was found between the shear bond strengths of BIOfactor MTA to flowable composite and to GIC (p<0.05). Similarly, Biodentine also exhibited a statistically significant difference in shear bond strength when bonded to flowable composite versus GIC (p<0.05). In both materials, higher bond strengths were observed with flowable composite.

A statistically significant difference in bond strength was found between the BIOfactor MTA–flowable composite group and the Biodentine–flowable composite group (p<0.05). Similarly, a statistically significant difference was observed between the BIOfactor MTA– GIC and Biodentine– GIC groups (p<0.05). In both comparisons, Biodentine demonstrated higher bond strength to the restorative materials than BIOfactor MTA. The classification of bond failures observed on the surfaces of the BIOfactor MTA and Biodentine specimens under a stereomicroscope is presented in Table 2. Representative images of the cohesive, adhesive, and mixed failure types observed are shown in Fig. 4.

4. Discussion

In endodontic practice, the use of calcium silicate-based materials such as MTA and Biodentine has become increasingly popular due to their successful clinical outcomes. This growing popularity has highlighted the need for further scientific research on the subject.

Although there is a general consensus that calcium silicate-based materials exhibit superior clinical performance compared to other materials in vital pulp therapies³, there is still no clear agreement in the literature regarding the most appropriate base

Table 2. Comparison of Shear Bond Strength Values (MPa) Between Materials

Materials	Adhesive	Cohesive	Mix	Total
BIOfactor MTA- Flowable Composite	6 (40%)	7 (47%)	2 (13%)	15
BIOfactor MTA-GIC	9 (60%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	15
Biodentine- Flowable Composite	4 (27%)	8 (53%)	3 (20%)	15
Biodentine-GIC	8 (53%)	2 (13%)	5 (34%)	15
Total	27	20	13	60

material to be placed over them.¹² Composite resins, GICs, and RMGICs are commonly recommended as base materials over calcium silicate-based materials.¹⁷ Composite resins demonstrate superior bonding strength to dentin and various materials due to their micromechanical bonding mechanisms and advanced adhesive technologies. However, concerns remain about their potential effects on the vital pulp, as they release high heat during polymerization and contain chemical monomers.¹⁸ In contrast, GIC is a biocompatible material composed of a glass matrix that includes elements such as Ca, F, and Al.¹⁹ In our study, we preferred to use flowable composite and GIC as base materials.

Biodentine completes its final setting reaction in approximately 85 minutes.²⁰ It is also known that MTA has certain disadvantages, such as a delayed setting time and challenging handling characteristics.²¹ To avoid applying physical force to the material during the setting phase, the use of flowable composite—capable of spreading over the bioceramic surface without exerting pressure—may be a more appropriate approach. Therefore, in our study, the resin-based material selected was a flowable composite. Our other base material was GIC, a biocompatible material composed of a glass matrix.

In a study comparing the shear bond strengths between MTA and composite resin using different adhesive systems, the total-etch technique—also employed in our study—demonstrated comparable shear bond strength.²² Similarly, in our research, the total-etch adhesive approach was used prior to the application of the flowable composite. Phosphoric acid, which is currently the most widely accepted and frequently used etchant, was also preferred in our study.

Our findings suggest that Biodentine exhibited higher shear bond strength than BIOfactor MTA to both flowable composite and GIC. When similar studies in the literature are examined, the findings of Gürcan et al.²³ also indicate that Biodentine exhibited higher bond strength values compared to BIOfactor MTA. However, in their study, this difference was not found to be statistically significant. In this respect, while both studies show a similar trend in terms of general outcomes, the statistical significance of the results differs. Moreover, Gürcan et al.²³ investigated various adhesive strategies and employed more complex protocols, whereas the present study focused on

Fig. 4. Cohesive (A), adhesive (B), and mixed (C) bond failures observed on the surfaces of BIOfactor MTA and Biodentine (from left to right).

simplified conditions using only flowable composite and conventional GIC. The fact that both studies were conducted independently and within a similar time frame highlights the growing scientific interest in this subject. It also emphasizes the value of assessing the same materials through different application techniques, thereby enriching the existing body of knowledge in the literature.

In another study investigating the shear bond strengths of MTA, Biodentine, GIC and composite resin to dentine, findings indicated that Biodentine exhibited higher bond strength than MTA, and composite resin adhered better than other materials.⁶ The higher bond strength of Biodentine could be attributed to the particle size that penetrates the dentinal tubules.²⁴ The more uniform and finer particle structure of Biodentine could provide better adhesion compared to BIOfactor MTA.

The limitations of the present study include the lack of evaluation of shear bond strength at different time intervals, as only the values at 24 hours were measured. Additionally, shear bond strength under different adhesive protocols was not assessed. In another study investigating time-dependent changes, Biodentine's shear bond strength was shown to increase significantly between 2 days and 1 week.²⁵ Furthermore, this was an in vitro study, and in vivo conditions such as the presence of blood, irrigants, and acidic environments may significantly alter the outcomes. Another point that differs from clinical procedures is that in this study, the materials were subjected to mechanical force only after completing their initial setting reaction.

However, in clinical scenarios, a 24-hour incubation period may not always be feasible, and both the tooth and the calcium silicate-based material may be exposed to occlusal forces shortly after placement. Despite the use of standardized Teflon molds and strict adherence to material preparation protocols, the bond strength data did not follow a normal distribution. This may be attributed to inherent variability in manual procedures such as mixing, specimen handling, and surface treatment, which are difficult to eliminate entirely even under controlled conditions. These minor deviations may have introduced variability in the physical properties of the test specimens and should be considered a methodological limitation of the study. Moreover, the flowable composite material was applied in 2 mm increments, consistent with the manufacturer's instructions, which permit application in layers of ≤ 2 mm using a dispensing tip. However, it is acknowledged that most manufacturers recommend a maximum increment thickness of 1 mm for optimal light polymerization. Although the protocol was in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines and thorough light curing was performed to enhance polymerization depth, it is possible that the use of a 2 mm increment may have influenced the degree of polymerization and, consequently, the bond strength outcomes. This potential limitation should be taken into consideration when interpreting the results. Further studies are warranted to investigate the impact of increment thickness on bond strength, particularly in relation to the material-specific polymerization characteristics and curing protocols.

5. Conclusion

Biodentine exhibited significantly higher shear bond strength to both flowable composite and GIC compared to BIOfactor MTA. Additionally, both calcium silicate-based cements demonstrated higher bond strength values when paired with flowable composite rather than GIC.

References

1. Al-Hiyasat AS, Ahmad DM, Khader YS. The effect of different calcium silicate-based pulp capping materials on tooth discoloration: an in vitro study. *BMC oral health*. 2021;21(1):330.
2. Kim SG, Malek M, Sigurdsson A, Lin LM, Kahler B.. Regenerative endodontics: a comprehensive review. *Int Endod J*. 2018;51(12):1367-1388.
3. Hilton TJ, Ferracane JL, Mancl L. Comparison of CaOH with MTA for direct pulp capping: a PBRN randomized clinical trial. *J Dent Res*. 2013;92(7 Suppl):16s-22s.
4. Odabaş ME, Bani M, Tiralı RE. Shear bond strengths of different adhesive systems to biodentine. *Sci World J*. 2013;2013:626103.
5. Hursh KA, Kirkpatrick TC, Cardon JW, Brewster JA, Black SW, Himel VT, et al. Shear Bond Comparison between 4 Bioceramic Materials and Dual-cure Composite Resin. *J Endod*. 2019;45(11):1378-1383.
6. Kaup M, Dammann CH, Schäfer E, Dammaschke T. Shear bond strength of Biodentine, ProRoot MTA, glass ionomer cement and composite resin on human dentine ex vivo. *Head Face Med*. 2015;11:14.
7. Boutsoukis C, Noula G, Lambrianidis T. Ex vivo study of the efficiency of two techniques for the removal of mineral trioxide aggregate used as a root canal filling material. *J Endod*. 2008;34(10):1239-1242.
8. Torabinejad M, Parirokh M, Dummer PMH.. Mineral trioxide aggregate and other bioactive endodontic cements: an updated overview - part II: other clinical applications and complications. *Int Endod J*. 2018;51(3):284-317.
9. Rajasekharan S, Martens LC, Cauwels RG, Verbeeck RM. Biodentine™ material characteristics and clinical applications: a review of the literature. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*. 2014;15(3):147-158.
10. Akbulut MB, Mutlu Ş N, Soylu MA, Şimşek E. Interfacial characteristics of BIOfactor MTA and Biodentine with dentin. *Microsc Res Tech*. 2023;86(2):258-267.
11. Özer H, Abaklı İnci M, Açar Tuzluca S. The push-out bond strength of three root canal materials used in primary teeth: in vitro study. *Front Dent Med*. 2023;4:1140794.
12. Morotomi T, Washio A, Kitamura C. Current and future options for dental pulp therapy. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev*. 2019;55(1):5-11.
13. Yesilyurt C, Yildirim T, Taşdemir T, Kusgoz A. Shear bond strength of conventional glass ionomer cements bound to mineral trioxide aggregate. *J Endod*. 2009;35(10):1381-1383.
14. Parirokh M, Torabinejad M. Mineral trioxide aggregate: a comprehensive literature review--Part III: Clinical applications, drawbacks, and mechanism of action. *J Endod*. 2010;36(3):400-413.
15. Peskersoy C, Lukarcanin J, Turkun M. Efficacy of different calcium silicate materials as pulp-capping agents: Randomized clinical trial. *J Dent Sci*. 2021;16(2):723-731.
16. Palma PJ, Marques JA, Antunes M, Falacho RI, Sequeira D, Roseiro L, et al. Effect of restorative timing on shear bond strength of composite resin/calcium silicate-based cements adhesive interfaces. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2021;25(5):3131-3139.
17. Cohenca N, Paranjpe A, Berg J. Vital pulp therapy. *Dent Clin North Am*. 2013;57(1):59-73.
18. Goldberg M. In vitro and in vivo studies on the toxicity of dental resin components: a review. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2008;12(1):1-8.
19. Schuur AH, Gruythuysen RJ, Wesselink PR. Pulp capping with adhesive resin-based composite vs. calcium hydroxide: a review. *Endod Dent Traumatol*. 2000;16(6):240-250.

20. Kaup M, Schäfer E, Dammaschke T. An in vitro study of different material properties of Biodentine compared to ProRoot MTA. *Head Face Med.* 2015;11:16.
21. Antonijevic D, Medigovic I, Zrilic M, Jokic B, Vukovic Z, Todorovic L. The influence of different radiopacifying agents on the radiopacity, compressive strength, setting time, and porosity of Portland cement. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2014;18(6):1597-1604.
22. Samimi P, Kazemian M, Shirban F, Alaei S, Khoroushi M. Bond strength of composite resin to white mineral trioxide aggregate: Effect of different surface treatments. *J Conserv Dent.* 2018;21(4):350-353.
23. Gürcan AT, Şişmanoğlu S, Sengez G. Effect of Different Adhesive Strategies on the Microshear Bond Strength of Calcium-Silicate-Based Materials. *J Adv Oral Res.* 2022;13(2):191-199.
24. Guneser MB, Akbulut MB, Eldeniz AU. Effect of various endodontic irrigants on the push-out bond strength of biodentine and conventional root perforation repair materials. *J Endod.* 2013;39(3):380-384.
25. Zapf AM, Chedella SC, Berzins DW. Effect of additives on mineral trioxide aggregate setting reaction product formation. *J Endod.* 2015;41(1):88-91.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

Ethics Approval

Since sources obtained from humans or animals were not used in this study, ethics committee approval was not obtained.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflict of interest and not have any financial interest in the companies whose materials are included in this article.

Original Article

Evaluation of Crown Removal Using Two Devices Manual Back Action vs Spring Loaded Press Type Crown Removers, A Randomized Clinical Trial

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The manual back-action crown remover offers
clinicians reliable method to preserve tooth
structure and allow restoration reuse,
reducing procedural risks and costs, while
automated devices may expedite removal but
carry higher risk of damage.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: While manual back-action devices rely on tactile feedback and controlled force, automated spring-loaded press-type removers offer ease of operation but may exert less predictable forces. This study aimed to compare the success rate, efficiency, and incidence of unexpected events between manual back-action and spring-loaded press-type crown removers.

Materials and Methods: In this randomized clinical trial, 140 crowns and bridges (70 per group) requiring removal were assigned to either a manual back-action remover (Group 1) or a spring-loaded press-type remover (Group 2). All procedures were performed by a single experienced endodontist under local anesthesia. Primary outcome was successful intact removal; secondary outcomes included procedure time and adverse events (catastrophic vs. non-catastrophic failures). Statistical comparisons were made using chi-square tests and independent t-tests.

Results: Overall success was high in both groups (Group 1: 87% [61/70]; Group 2: 91% [64/70]; $p > 0.05$). Mean removal time did not differ significantly (Group 1: 6 ± 5 min; Group 2: 5 ± 3 min; $p > 0.05$). However, the manual back-action group experienced significantly fewer unexpected events (20% vs. 47%; $p = 0.046$), including lower rates of coronal tooth fractures (4% vs. 11%) and crown chipping (4% vs. 24%). Reuse of restorations was higher after manual removal (80% vs. 56%; $p = 0.002$).

Conclusion: Both devices are effective for crown and bridge removal, achieving comparable success rates and procedure times. The manual back-action remover, however, yields a significantly lower incidence of adverse events and greater preservation of restorations. Clinicians should consider manual removal when conservation of tooth structure and prosthesis reuse are priorities.

1. Introduction

The increasing prevalence of periodontal diseases, dental caries, and tooth loss continues to impact global oral health, affecting nearly half of the world's population.^{1,2} Dental crowns and bridges are routinely used to restore function and aesthetics in both root canal-treated and edentulous cases, providing strength, longevity, and improved patient satisfaction.^{3,4} The long-term success of such restorations depends on adequate sealing and adaptation, which are essential to prevent bacterial infiltration and reinfection of the underlying tooth structure.^{5,6}

Despite advances in restorative materials and techniques, dental crowns and bridges are not permanent. Clinical studies indicate that the mean lifespan of crowns is approximately 10 years, with six-year survival rates around 88%.^{9,10} Over time, several clinical scenarios may necessitate the removal of these restorations, including endodontic retreatment, development of secondary caries, marginal adaptation issues, chipping or fracture of the ceramic layer, and periodontal complications such as gingival recession or bone loss.^{7,8} In some cases, removal is required to facilitate accurate diagnosis and treatment planning, particularly when the underlying condition of the abutment tooth is uncertain or compromised.^{11,12}

Traditionally, dental restorations can be removed using either destructive or conservative methods. Destructive techniques involve sectioning and irreversibly damaging the restoration, thus preventing any possibility of reuse and increasing treatment time and cost for the patient.¹⁵ In contrast, conservative approaches aim to dislodge the crown or bridge while preserving its structural integrity, enabling possible recementation and reducing both patient morbidity and financial burden.^{15,16} The choice of removal

technique is influenced by factors such as abutment design, periodontal status, type of restorative material, and the presence of posts or cores.^{13,14}

A wide range of conservative removal devices have been developed to facilitate atraumatic crown and bridge removal. However, despite their frequent use in clinical practice, there is a lack of well-designed comparative studies evaluating the effectiveness and safety of these devices. A preliminary search of the literature reveals no randomized clinical trials directly comparing commonly used conservative removal tools.

The primary aim of this randomized clinical trial is to compare the success rates of two conservative crown and bridge removal devices: the manual back-action remover and the spring-loaded press-type remover. Success is defined as the removal of crowns or bridges in toto (i.e., intact and without irreparable damage). The secondary objective is to evaluate and compare the incidence of procedural complications and adverse events occurring during and after the removal process with each device.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Trial design

The study design is a randomized clinical trial and was conducted following approval by the Institutional ethical committee board (CSICDSR/IEC/0282/2023) at CSI College of Dental Sciences and Research. The trial was registered at Clinical Trial Registry India (CTRI/2023/12/060538). The current study was performed between January 2023 to December 2023.

Fig. 1. Treatment using Manual back action crown remover

2.2. Sample size calculation

Sample size was determined through G Power software version 3.1.9.2 with effect size of 0.37 with alpha error 0.05 and power 0.95 gives a total sample size of 140 crowns and bridges.

2.3. Participants, eligibility criteria

The study included both root canal treated and vital teeth that had been restored with single-unit crowns, as well as crowns or bridges comprising up to three units. Eligible restorations included metal crowns, metal-ceramic crowns, Emax crowns, zirconia crowns, and ceramic-faced crowns. Teeth with severe periodontal compromise and restorations involving more than three units (i.e., large bridges) were excluded from the study.

2.4. Interventions

A comprehensive medical evaluation was conducted for all participants, and each patient was informed about the potential risks and benefits prior to the procedure.¹⁸ Pre-operative radiographs were taken to assess the periodontal status of the tooth, including the presence of periapical radiolucency, bone loss, and the quality of obturation. Pre-treatment clinical photographs were obtained using a DSLR camera under standardized lighting conditions.

The subjects were randomly assigned to one of two groups using the lottery method. One group underwent crown removal using a

manual back-action crown remover, while the other group was treated with a spring-loaded press-type crown remover. All procedures were performed by a single experienced endodontist.¹⁷ All procedures were performed under local anesthesia (1:80,000 Lignocaine hydrochloride with adrenaline; Lignox, Warren Pharmaceuticals, India).

In Group 1 (manual back-action), 70 crowns and bridges (58 single-unit crowns and 12 joint crowns) were attempted for removal. The tip of the crown remover was secured to the margins of the crowns and bridges with the thumb of the left hand, while the other hand supported the weight of the remover attached to the shaft. Each stroke was generated manually by gently sliding the weight along the hammer shaft to deliver short and rapid impact forces, thereby aiding in the dislodgement of the crowns and bridges (Fig. 1).

In Group 2 (spring-loaded press-type), 70 crowns and bridges (56 single-unit crowns and 14 joint crowns) were attempted for removal. This device was operated single-handedly; the tip of the crown remover engaged the margins of the crowns and bridges, and with a simple press of the handle, the device automatically generated the necessary force for crown dislodgement (Fig. 2).

Success in this study was defined as the complete removal of crowns and bridges with minimal damage to both the restorations and the underlying tooth structure. Following each successful

Fig. 2. Treatment using spring press type crown remover.

CONSORT 2010 Flow Diagram

Fig. 3. Pirate flowchart

removal, post-operative radiographs and clinical photographs were taken to assess the remaining tooth structure and the crown-to-root ratio. Further evaluation was performed to determine if the crowns could be re-luted, provided that the margin fit was satisfactory.

Failure was defined as an unsuccessful attempt to remove crowns and bridges with the assigned device, necessitating removal by sectioning using a diamond or tungsten carbide bur or metal cutting bur. A catastrophic failure was defined as a coronal fracture of the tooth resulting in extensive damage and requiring a change in treatment plan with more complex and costly interventions. A non-catastrophic failure referred to marginal breakdown of the restoration, crown chipping, or crown fracture causing only minimal tooth damage, usually requiring minor adjustments without the need for complex intervention.

2.5. Primary and secondary outcome

The primary outcome of this study was the success rate of crown and bridge removal using the manual back-action crown remover compared to the spring-loaded press-type crown remover. Success was defined as the complete removal of the crown or bridge with minimal damage to the restoration and the underlying tooth structure.

The secondary outcome was the evaluation of any unexpected events or complications that occurred during or after the crown removal procedures. These included both catastrophic and non-catastrophic failures, as well as any adverse effects observed postoperatively.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS software version 23 (IBM Corp., USA) to evaluate the overall success rate of

Table 1. Success rates of crown removal using two devices

Instrument	Successful	Unsuccessful	Total
Manual back action	61 (87.1%)	9 (12.9%)	70
Spring-loaded automatic	64 (91.4%)	6 (8.6%)	70
Total	125 (89.3%)	15 (10.7%)	140
p-value	0.672		

crown removal, the time required to complete the procedure, and the unexpected event during and after crown removal between the two groups were compared using the chi-square test.

3. Results

The average age of the patients in this study was 40 ± 13 years. A total of 140 crowns and bridges were evaluated, including 114 single crowns and 26 splinted (joint) crowns. The distribution by type was as follows: 27 metal crowns, 95 metal-ceramic crowns, 10 zirconia crowns, 5 ceramic-facing crowns, and 3 E-Max crowns. The study included 54 male and 73 female patients, with each gender group receiving 70 crowns and bridges (Fig. 3).

The success rate of crown removal was evaluated, yielding an overall success rate of 89% (124 out of 140 crowns and bridges; 103 single crowns and 21 joint crowns). In Group 1 (Manual back-action), 61 out of 70 crowns and bridges were successfully removed (52 single crowns and 9 joint crowns), corresponding to a success rate of 87%. In Group 2 (Spring-loaded press type), 63 out of 70 crowns and bridges were successfully removed (51 single crowns and 12 joint crowns), resulting in a 91% success rate. However, the difference in success rates between the groups was not statistically significant (p > 0.05) (Table 1).

The time required for successful crown removal was compared between the two groups. In Group 1 (Manual back-action), the mean duration for removing crowns and bridges was approximately 6 ± 5 minutes (61 cases), whereas in Group 2 (Spring-loaded press type), the mean duration was 5 ± 3 minutes (63 cases). Although the difference was not statistically significant, the manual back-action group required more time for crown removal compared to the spring-loaded press type group.

A total of 48 unexpected events occurred during and after crown removal. In Group 1 (Manual back-action), there were 14 unexpected events: 5 restoration fractures, 2 crown fractures, 1 tooth luxation, 3 coronal tooth fractures, and 3 instances of chipping of crowns and bridges. In Group 2 (Spring-loaded press type), there were 33 unexpected events: 8 restoration fractures, 8 coronal tooth fractures, and 17 instances of chipping of crowns and bridges (Table 2). There was a statistically significant difference in the incidence of unexpected events between the two groups (P = 0.046). The highest incidence of coronal tooth fractures was observed in premolar cases, affecting both maxillary and mandibular premolars (n=8). In this study, catastrophic failures occurred more frequently in single-unit crowns compared to joint crowns.

The reuse of crowns and bridges after removal was achieved in 56 cases (51 single crowns and 5 joint crowns) in Group 1 (manual

Table 2. Unexpected events during and after crown removal by instrument

Event	Manual back-action type — n (%)	Spring-loaded press type — n (%)	P-Value
Catastrophic Failures			
Coronal fracture of tooth	3 (21.4%)	8 (24.2%)	
Subtotal — catastrophic failures	3 (21.4%)	8 (24.2%)	
Non-Catastrophic Failures			
Restoration failure	5 (35.7%)	8 (24.2%)	0.046
Crown fracture	2 (14.3%)	0 (0.0%)	
Crown chipping	3 (21.4%)	17 (51.5%)	
Tooth luxation	1 (7.1%)	0 (0.0%)	
Subtotal — non-catastrophic failures	11 (78.6%)	25 (75.8%)	
Total (all unexpected events)	14 (100.0%)	33 (100.0%)	

Fig. 4. Reuse of crown and bridges

back-action crown remover), and in 39 cases (36 single crowns and 3 joint crowns) in Group 2 (spring-loaded press type crown remover). This difference was statistically significant ($P = 0.002$) (Fig. 4).

4. Discussion

Crown failure can result from a variety of factors, including endodontic failure, secondary caries, periodontal disease, excessive bridge span, ceramic fractures, and loosening.¹⁸ Successful crown removal requires meticulous planning to minimize the risk of injury to the underlying tissues. In addition to the traditional cutting method, several alternative techniques have been developed to facilitate crown removal while preserving tooth structure.¹⁹

The primary objective of this study was to compare the success rates of two crown removal devices: the manual back-action remover and the spring-loaded press type remover. Both devices demonstrated effective performance, with no statistically significant difference in overall success rates between the manual back-action group and the spring-loaded press type group.

In the present study, several unexpected events were encountered during crown and bridge removal, including chipping of the crown, crown fracture, and tooth luxation. In addition, restoration fracture and coronal tooth fracture were observed after the removal of crowns and bridges. The causes of these events are likely related to factors such as the grip of the devices and the amount of force or stress exerted on the tooth structure. While a firm grip is necessary to loosen crowns and bridges,²⁰ it may inadvertently contribute to crown chipping and fracture. Misdirected or excessive forces can damage the underlying tooth or core²¹, and excessive force or stress may lead to restoration fracture, coronal tooth fracture, or even tooth luxation.²²

In this study, a higher number of unexpected events were observed in the spring-loaded press type group, likely due to the stronger gripping force and greater uncontrolled pressure exerted by the automatic device, resulting in increased stress on the tooth structure. Furthermore, premolar teeth were more frequently associated with coronal fractures during removal with both types of crown removers, probably due to their smaller size and reduced ability to withstand traction forces during crown removal.²³ Tooth luxation occurred during manual back-action crown removal, which was attributed to moderately compromised periodontal health. Therefore, it is advisable to use both devices with caution, especially in cases with moderate or severe periodontal compromise.

Although the manual back-action crown remover was associated with fewer adverse events, it presented challenges in achieving a firm grip on the crown, which often made dislodgement more time-consuming. In contrast, the spring-loaded press type group provided greater stability and a more secure hold at multiple points. However, barriers such as limited access can also affect

treatment outcomes.²⁴ Crown removal in posterior regions, such as second molars, is particularly difficult in patients with limited mouth opening. Restricted access and limited visibility hinder proper instrument positioning and angulation, thereby increasing the risk of slippage and prolonging the procedure when using the manual back-action device. These findings suggest that while both techniques are effective, the press type method offers practical advantages in terms of ease of handling and operator comfort in challenging access situations. Notably, during this study, the spring-loaded press-type crown remover device required replacement midway, as the spring action force gradually diminished, rendering the device ineffective. In contrast, the manual back-action remover remained functional throughout the study and did not require replacement.

One of the main objectives in crown removal is to adopt a conservative approach that preserves the underlying tooth structure and minimizes unnecessary damage to crowns and bridges, thereby facilitating their potential reusability. Intactly removed crowns and bridges can be reused as provisional restorations during the fabrication of new prostheses.²² In the present study, a higher number of coronal tooth fractures was observed in the spring-loaded press type group, likely due to the uncontrolled forces exerted by this device, which can make it difficult for the operator to precisely sense and control the amount of force applied during crown and bridge removal. Additionally, crown chipping is a critical factor affecting the reusability of prostheses. The results of this study showed that the spring-loaded press type crown remover resulted in a higher incidence of crown chipping, which hindered the reusability of crowns, compared to the manual back-action crown remover. This may be attributed to the manual device's ability to apply controlled and gradual force based on the operator's tactile feedback.¹³

Although the overall success rate and the time required for removal of crowns and bridges were similar between the two devices, the extent of damage to both the tooth and the crown differed significantly. The automatic (spring-loaded press type) crown remover was found to be more destructive than the manual method, causing greater damage to both the tooth structure and the existing crown. In contrast, the manual technique allowed for more controlled and gradual removal. Therefore, the manual back-action approach is particularly advantageous in preserving the original restoration, reducing additional costs, and minimizing the need for a new prosthesis.²⁵

The primary limitation of this study is its single-center design with all procedures performed by one operator, which may restrict the applicability of our findings to other clinical settings and experience levels. The relatively small sample size and the necessity to replace the spring-loaded press device midway—due to mechanical power degradation—could have introduced variability and limit the consistency of the performance data.

5. Conclusion

Both the manual back-action and spring-loaded press-type crown removers achieved similarly high success rates and comparable procedure durations. However, the manual technique consistently produced less damage to both the tooth structure and the existing restoration, underscoring its value when preservation of the prosthesis and underlying dentition is paramount. The automated device, while offering user-convenience and streamlined operation, carries a greater risk of coronal fractures and restoration damage. Clinicians should therefore select the crown removal method that best balances operative efficiency with the need for restorative conservation. Ongoing refinement of device mechanics and the development of standardized training protocols may further improve clinical outcomes and broaden the applicability of automated removal systems.

References

- Rajasekaran JJ, Krishnamurthy HK, Bosco J, Jayaraman V, Krishna K, Wang T, Bei K. Oral microbiome: a review of its impact on oral and systemic health. *Microorganisms*. 2024; 12(9):1797
- Perrone BR, Bottesini VC, Duarte DA. Minimal intervention dentistry: What is its clinical application and effectiveness in different continents? –A scoping review. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2024; 27(2):134-139.
- Benisha RE, Piriyaanga R, Sherwood IA, Ramanathan IS, Abirami AA. Comparing metal onlay and full crown in root canal treated molars with single proximal defect - An 18-month clinical study. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2025; 28(5):468-473.
- Patel J, Shah NC, Dedania M, Choudhary D, Bharti N, Jain A. Comparative clinical evaluation of correct anatomic contour and tight contact in Class II direct composite restoration using two newer contact forming instruments. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2024; 27(11):1135-1140.
- Anand M, Karthikeyan K, Sekar M. Current trend of restoration of endodontically treated teeth with extensive subgingival caries: A case series. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2022; 25(2):202-205.
- Heling I, Gorfil C, Slutzky H, Kopolovic K, Zalkind M, Slutzky-Goldberg I. Endodontic failure caused by inadequate restorative procedures: review and treatment recommendations. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2002; 87(6):674-678.
- Algadhi AA, Aljuman AS, Hummadi AM, Alqunfuthi NI, Al Moaleem MM. Crown or Not to Crown Root Canal Treated Teeth: Minireview. *Biosc Biotech Res Comm*. 2021; 14(2): 594-599.
- Goodacre CJ, Bernal G, Rungcharassaeng K, Kan JY. Clinical complications in fixed Prosthodontics. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2003; 90(1):31-41.
- Schwartz NL, Whitsett LD, Berry TG, Stewart JL. Unserviceable crowns and fixed partial dentures: life-span and causes for loss of serviceability. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 1970; 81(6):1395-1401.
- Raedel M, Priess HW, Bohm S, Walter MH. Six-year survival of single crowns - A massive data analysis. *J Dent*. 2020; 101:103459.
- Parreira FR, O'Connor RP, Hutter JW. Cast prosthesis removal using ultrasonics and a thermoplastic resin adhesive. *J Endod*. 1994; 20(3):141-143.
- Addy LD, Bartley A, Hayes SJ. Crown and bridge disassembly--when, why and how. *Dent Update*. 2007; 34(3):140-150.
- Biswas M, Mazumdar D, Gengadharani B, Saha KK, Saha B, Saha D. Comparative evaluation of fracture resistance of endodontically treated teeth with wedge shaped non-carious cervical lesions using different types of esthetic post: An in vitro study. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2025; 28(3):285-289.
- Janardanan K, Varkey VK, Lovely M, Anuroopa A. Coronal disassembly systems and techniques: An overview. *J Interdiscip Dent*. 2014; 4(1):33.
- Raghavan R, Shajahan PA, Gibi MV. Crown Removers: A Review. *Int J Innov Sci Res Technol*. 2022;7(4):751-755.
- Vasileva R. Techniques for fixed dental restorations removal – classification, decision on the correct approach, advantages and disadvantages. *J IMAB*. 2021;27(1):3510-3517
- Corah NL, Gale EN, Illig SJ. Assessment of a dental anxiety scale. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 1978; 97(5):816-819.
- Zavanelli AC, Mazaró JV, Nóbrega PI, Falcón-antenucc RM, Zavanelli RA. Data collection about failures in fixed partial dentures: 1-year monitoring. *RGO-Rev Gaúch Odontol*. 2018; 66(3):250-256.
- Alhaddad AJ, Abuzinadah SH, Alkhalifah T. Recent techniques for removal of indirect restorations: classification and minimally invasive approach. *Ann Med Health Sci Res*. 2021; 11(6):31-36
- Larsson A, Manuh J, Chrcanovic BR. Risk factors associated with failure and technical complications of implant-supported single crowns: A retrospective study. *Medicina*. 2023; 59(9):1603.
- Varghese VS, Uppin V, Pujar M, Kurian N, Barad N. Crown removal approaches: regaining entry to the pulp chamber. *Indian J Appl Res*. 2016; 6(3):245-248.
- Sharma A, Rahul GR, Poduval ST, Shetty K. Removal of failed crown and bridge. *J Clin Exp Dent*. 2012; 4(3):167-172.
- Ozkir SE, Unal SM, Yurekli E, Güven S. Effects of crown retrieval on implants and the surrounding bone: a finite element analysis. *J Adv prosthodont*. 2016; 8(2):131-136.
- da Rosa SV, Moysés SJ, Theis LC, Soares RC, Moysés ST, Werneck RI, Rocha JS. Barriers in access to dental services hindering the treatment of people with disabilities: a systematic review. *Int J Dent*. 2020; 2020:1-17.
- Bajunaid SO. Review of techniques for the intact removal of a permanently cemented restoration. *Gen Dent*. 2017; 65(5):48-53.

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Data Availability Statement

Data can be shared on genuine request to corresponding author.

Ethics Approval

Clinical Trial Registry India with CTRI number (<https://www.ctri.nic.in>) CTRI/2023/12/060538. following approval by the Institutional ethical committee board (CSICDSR/IEC/0282/2023).

Conflict of Interest

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Original Article

Investigation of the Color Change on Nano-Hybrid Composite Resin Caused by Non-Hydrogen Peroxide Whitening Mouthwashes

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Non-hydrogen peroxide whitening mouthrinses can cause perceptible color changes on nano-hybrid composite restorations; clinicians should consider these effects when recommending them to patients with anterior restorations.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to examine the color change on nano-hybrid composite resin caused by non-peroxide whitening mouthrinses.

Materials and Methods: A nano-hybrid composite resin (shade A3) was used to prepare fifty disc-shaped specimens (8 mm in diameter and 2 mm in thickness) using a custom-made PTFE mold. Polymerization was performed with an LED light-curing unit according to the manufacturer's instructions, applying light for 20 seconds on each side. The specimens were then stored in distilled water at 37 °C for 24 hours. Subsequently, they were randomly assigned into five subgroups (n = 10): four experimental groups treated with whitening mouthrinses (Listerine Advanced White [LAW], Colgate Optic White [COW], Colgate Plax White Charcoal [CPWC], Splat White Plus [SWP]) and one control group (distilled water). Color measurements were performed at baseline (T0) and after a 4-week mouthrinse regimen (T1) using a spectrophotometer (VITA Easyshade Compact, VITA Zahnfabrik, Bad Säckingen, Germany) based on the CIELAB system. Color difference (ΔE_{00}) and whiteness index difference (ΔWID) values were calculated.

Results: Significant differences were found among groups ($p < 0.05$). All experimental groups exhibited perceptible color changes ($\Delta E_{00} > 0.8$), while LAW, COW, CPWC, and SWP exceeded the acceptability threshold ($\Delta E_{00} > 1.8$). SWP demonstrated the highest color and whiteness change, showing statistically significant differences from other groups ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Non-peroxide whitening mouthrinses caused clinically acceptable color changes on nano-hybrid composite resin. SWP, which contains bromelain, exhibited the highest whitening effect.

1. Introduction

Aesthetic teeth and a flawless smile have become one of the most common reasons for patients to visit dentists today. In response to this need, patients' interest in tooth whitening has been increasing. Tooth whitening treatments have become a focus of interest for researchers, and as a result of studies, new whitening products are being introduced to the market.¹ Moreover, access to over-the-counter (OTC) whitening products has become widespread. There are various whitening products available on the market, including mouth rinses, toothpastes, dental floss, whitening strips, and chewing gums. Nowadays, patients can easily purchase these products from supermarkets, pharmacies, and online. Most of these products are inexpensive alternatives to tooth whitening treatments performed by dentists.²

One of the OTC products recommended by dentists is mouth rinses. These products are generally recommended for plaque control and gum health. Recently, whitening mouth rinses containing different ratios of hydrogen peroxide or various chemicals have been introduced to the market.³ Whitening mouth rinses are produced to prevent tooth stains and quickly whiten teeth. They have become one of the most popular OTC products due to their ease of use by patients and low cost.⁴ Some whitening mouth rinses do not contain hydrogen or carbamide peroxide as active ingredients.⁵ Although most studies have focused on whitening mouth rinses containing hydrogen peroxide, their whitening effects are significantly lower compared to professional whitening treatments.⁶ Mouth rinses containing hydrogen peroxide pose potential risks due to their low pH and uncontrolled application in the mouth. Cytogenetic damage, chemical burns on the gums, and dentin erosion have been considered potential side effects of hydrogen peroxide-containing mouth rinses.⁷⁻¹⁰

Alternatively, whitening mouth rinses without hydrogen peroxide have been developed using ingredients such as sodium hexametaphosphate, tetrasodium pyrophosphate, and phthalimidoperoxycaproic acid.^{9,11,12} Additionally, there are whitening mouth rinses on the market containing bromelain, a natural component derived from pineapple, and activated charcoal, although research on these products remains scarce.

The agents used during whitening can affect not only the teeth but also existing restorations, causing color changes.¹³ Due to their organic matrix, resin composites are more susceptible to chemical changes caused by the acidic content of whitening agents compared to other restorative materials.¹⁴ Over time, intrinsic and extrinsic discoloration can occur in composite restorations. Intrinsic discoloration includes changes that can occur in the resin structure, resin matrix, and the interface of filler particles.¹⁵ Extrinsic discoloration, on the other hand, occurs due to adsorption or absorption of exogenous colorants such as coffee, tea, nicotine, and beverages.^{16,17} This discoloration in composite restorations may cause color mismatches and compromise aesthetics, leading to the replacement of time-consuming and costly restorations.¹⁸ Surface stains in composite resin restorations can be removed by techniques such as polishing, brushing, and whitening.¹⁹ For these reasons, the effects of whitening agents on resin composites need to be fully understood. Among whitening techniques, mouth rinses are among the most popular oral hygiene and tooth whitening products due to their ease of use, low cost, and accessibility.¹⁸ Most studies have tested the color change on stained composite restorations using hydrogen peroxide-containing whitening mouth rinses. However, the literature reveals insufficient information regarding the effects of hydrogen peroxide-free mouth rinses on unstained composite resins. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the color change on nano-hybrid composite

resin caused by hydrogen peroxide-free whitening mouth rinses developed to avoid the harmful effects of hydrogen peroxide used in whitening.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Preparation

A nano-hybrid composite resin (Clearfil Performance Pro, Kuraray Noritake Dental, Okayama, Japan) in shade A3 was used. Fifty disc-shaped specimens were prepared using a custom-made polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) mold with a diameter of 8 mm and a thickness of 2 mm. For the polymerization of the composite specimens, an LED light-curing device (VALO Cordless LED, Ultradent, South Jordan, UT, USA) was applied perpendicularly to both the top and bottom surfaces for 20 seconds, following the manufacturer's instructions. The prepared specimens were stored in distilled water at 37°C for the first 24 hours. The composite resin specimens were divided into five subgroups (n=10): four groups for different whitening mouth rinses and one control group using distilled water. The mouth rinses used in the study were as follows: Listerine Advanced White (LAW), Colgate Optic White (COW), Colgate Plax White Charcoal (CPWC), and Splat White Plus (SWP). The ingredients and details of the mouth rinses and restorative materials used in the study are presented in Table 1. After the composite resin specimens were divided into groups, each specimen in all groups was numbered from 1 to 10.

2.2. Color Measurement

The color values of each specimen were measured using a spectrophotometer (VITA Easyshade Compact, VITA Zahnfabrik, Bad Säckingen, Germany) with the Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE) $L^*a^*b^*$ system. The spectrophotometer was calibrated before each measurement according to the manufacturer's instructions. CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ values were recorded, where L^* indicates lightness from white to black (100–0), a^* represents the red-green chromatic coordinates, and b^* represents the yellow-blue chromatic coordinates. The color and whiteness changes of the specimens were calculated according to CIEDE2000 (ΔE_{00})²⁰ and the Whiteness Index for Dentistry (WI_D)²¹, respectively. Three readings were obtained for each specimen, and the average was calculated. For the ΔE_{00} index, the clinically acceptable value is 1.8, while the perceptible value is 0.8. For the WI_D index, these values are 2.6 and 0.7, respectively.²²

$$\Delta E_{00} =$$

$$[(\Delta L' / K_L S_L)^2 + (\Delta C' / K_C S_C)^2 + (\Delta H' / K_H S_H)^2 + R_T * (\Delta C' / K_C S_C) * (\Delta H' / K_H S_H)]^{1/2}$$

$$WI_D = 0.511 L^* - 2.324 a^* - 1.100 b^*$$

$$\Delta WI_D = WI_{D T1} - WI_{D T0}$$

In the CIEDE2000 (ΔE_{00}) equation, $\Delta L'$, $\Delta C'$, and $\Delta H'$ refer to the differences in lightness, chroma, and hue measurements before and after the procedure, respectively. S_L , S_C , and S_H are weighting functions added to the formula to correct irregularities observed in the CIELAB system. k_L , k_C , and k_H are parametric factors correcting for experimental conditions. R_T (rotation function) determines the interaction between chroma and hue changes in the blue region. In the whiteness index (WI_D) equation for dentistry, higher WI_D values indicate whiter specimens, while lower values (including negative) indicate darker specimens. Measurements were taken at baseline (T0) and after the 4-week mouth rinse cycle procedure (T1).

2.3. Mouthwashes Cycle Procedure

After the initial measurements (T0) were completed, each composite group was immersed in 25 mL of the respective mouth rinse. The specimens were shaken continuously for 60 seconds and then rinsed under running water for 30 seconds. Subsequently, they were placed in a refreshed mouth rinse solution for another 60 seconds. This procedure represented the twice-daily use of mouth rinses for 60 seconds.²³ The procedure was repeated seven times to simulate one week of use. Afterwards, the specimens were stored in distilled water for one day. The same procedure was repeated four times to simulate four weeks of use. Specimens were always kept in distilled water until the next experimental cycle, and upon completion of this stage, color measurements were repeated (T1).

2.4. Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics (number, percentage, mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum) were presented. The assumption of normal distribution was checked with the Shapiro-Wilk test, and the homogeneity of variances was tested with the Levene test. For the comparison of three or more independent groups with a normal distribution, the ANOVA test was used. Post Hoc Bonferroni tests were performed to determine which group or groups caused the differences. Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS 27 software. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Table 1. Chemical compositions and manufacturers of the mouth rinses and restorative materials used in the study

Product	Manufacturer	Components
Listerine Advanced White Mouth Rinse	Johnson & Johnson, Skillman, NJ, USA	Water, Alcohol, Sorbitol, Tetrapotassium Pyrophosphate, Pentasodium Triphosphate, Citric Acid, Poloxamer 407, Flavors, Sodium Saccharin, Sucralose, Sodium Fluoride, Sodium Benzoate, Tetrasodium Pyrophosphate, Menthol, Eucalyptol, Thymol, Flavor, Propylene Glycol, Disodium Phosphate
Colgate Plax White And Charcoal Mouth Rinse	Colgate-Palmolive, Guildford, GU2 8JZ	Water, Glycerin, Propylene Glycol, Sorbitol, Tetrapotassium Pyrophosphate, Polysorbate 20, Tetrasodium Pyrophosphate, Zinc Citrate, PVM/MA Copolymer, Flavor, Benzyl Alcohol, Sodium Fluoride, Sodium Saccharin, Bambusa Vulgaris Shoot Extract, Charcoal Powder, CI 15510, CI 17200, CI 19140, CI 42051
Colgate Optic White Mouth Rinse	GABA International AG, Therwil, Switzerland	Water, Glycerin, Sorbitol, Propylene Glycol, PVM/MA Copolymer, Tetrapotassium Pyrophosphate, Polysorbate 20, Sodium Fluoride, Sodium Saccharin, CI 42051
Splat White Plus Mouth Rinse	Splat Global, Russia	Aqua, Hydrogenated Starch Hydrolysate, PVP, Polyglyceryl-4 Laurate/Sebacate, Polyglyceryl-6 Caprylate/Caprate, Sodium Coco-Sulfate, Flavor, Cyclodextrin, Zinc Gluconate, Citrus Limon Peel Oil, Ananas Sativus Fruit Extract, Maltodextrin, Thymus Serpillum Oil, Glycyrrhiza Glabra Root Extract, Stevia Rebaudiana Leaf Extract, Glycerin, Pentylene Glycol, Bifida Ferment Lysate, Phthalimidoperoxyacaproic Acid, Potassium Thiocyanate, Lactoferrin, Lactoperoxidase, Glucose Oxidase, Glucose Pentaacetate, Sodium Benzoate, Potassium Sorbate, Benzyl Alcohol, Citric Acid, Limonene, Citral, Linalool
Clearfil Performance Pro Composite	Kuraray Noritake Dental, Okayama, Japan	Silanated barium glass (30–80%), Pre-polymerized organic filler ($\leq 40\%$), Bisphenol A diglycidyl methacrylate (5–15%), Hydrophobic aromatic dimethacrylate (5–15%), Silanated colloidal silica (1–5%), Hydrophobic aliphatic dimethacrylate (1–5%), dl-Camphorquinone ($\leq 0.1\%$)

Table 2. Distribution and comparison of ΔWI_D and ΔE_{00} measurements according to study groups

		Min.-Max.	Mean \pm S.D.	Median	Test Statistic	p
ΔWI_D	Distilled Water	-4.64/3.29	-0.98 \pm 2.57	-0.41	11.736	<0.001*
	CPWC	-9.38/-0.05	-4.43 \pm 3.28	-3.40		
	LAW	-9.53/11.86	2.28 \pm 6.34	1.93		
	COW	-1.85/8.72	2.05 \pm 3.35	1.12		
	SWP	1.65/13.11	7.14 \pm 3.10	6.58		
ΔE_{00}	Distilled Water	0.50/2.11	1.31 \pm 0.50	1.28	3.535	0.014*
	CPWC	1.06/4.27	2.23 \pm 0.96	1.99		
	LAW	0.83/3.99	2.15 \pm 1.09	2.08		
	COW	0.70/4.16	2.20 \pm 1.06	1.95		
	SWP	1.76/5.48	2.94 \pm 1.12	2.72		

*p<0.05

3. Results

The mean ΔE_{00} and ΔWI_D distributions and their comparisons obtained as a result of this study are shown in Table 2. The distributions of ΔWI_D and ΔE_{00} measurements according to the study groups are presented in the table, and ANOVA tests were used for comparisons. As a result of the analyses, statistically significant differences were found among the groups regarding ΔWI_D and ΔE_{00} measurements ($p < 0.05$).

According to the Bonferroni tests conducted for ΔWI_D , statistically significant differences were observed between Distilled Water and SWP ($p < 0.001$) and between CPWC and LAW, COW, and SWP ($p = 0.004$, $p = 0.007$, and $p < 0.001$, respectively). The SWP measurements were higher than CPWC measurements. LAW, COW, and SWP measurements were higher than distilled water measurements.

According to the Bonferroni tests conducted for ΔE_{00} , statistically significant differences were determined between Distilled Water and SWP ($p = 0.005$). The SWP measurements were higher than the distilled water measurements.

4. Discussion

Various color systems, such as CIE Lab* (ΔE_{ab}) and CIEDE2000 (ΔE_{00}), are commonly used in the analysis of color changes. However, studies have indicated that the CIEDE2000 color system is superior to the CIE Lab* system in determining perceptibility and acceptability.^{24,22} Therefore, in our study, the CIEDE2000 (ΔE_{00}) color system and formula were used for analyzing color changes.

When the literature is reviewed, various opinions are found regarding the perceptibility and acceptability of color changes in restorations.²⁵ A recent study defined the perceptibility threshold of the ΔE_{00} index as 0.8 and the acceptability threshold as 1.8.²² When the ΔE_{00} values obtained from our study were evaluated, it was observed that all groups were above the perceptibility threshold ($\Delta E_{00} > 0.8$), and effective whitening was achieved in all groups except the control group ($\Delta E_{00} > 1.8$). Therefore, hydrogen peroxide-free whitening mouth rinses provided acceptable color changes on nano-hybrid composite resin.

Formulas such as ΔE_{ab} and ΔE_{00} used to analyze color differences after tooth whitening do not provide sufficient information about changes in tooth whiteness.^{26,21,27} In this study, ΔWI_D , based on CIE Lab* coordinates, was used to evaluate changes in whiteness. A previous study defined the perceptibility threshold of the ΔWI_D index as 0.7 and the acceptability threshold as 2.6.²² According to our findings, all groups except the control group met the perceptibility threshold, while only the CPWC and SWP groups met the acceptability threshold. Statistically, the SWP group was superior to the CPWC group. This may be attributed to the whitening effect of bromelain, a proteolytic enzyme derived from

from pineapple. This enzyme breaks down organic compounds responsible for extrinsic stains,²⁸ thereby allowing light to reflect more easily from the surface and producing a brighter appearance.²⁹

Hydrogen peroxide is the most commonly used whitening agent both in clinical and at-home treatments.^{30,31} This agent is a strong oxidizer that facilitates whitening by breaking long-chain organic pigment molecules into shorter-chain compounds.³² However, due to its short shelf life and safety limitations, its use in mouth rinses is problematic. The whitening effects of the mouth rinses used in our study may be attributed to the active charcoal in CPWC, tetrasodium pyrophosphate in LAW, Patent Blue V (color index 42,051) providing optical properties in COW, and bromelain in SWP. Acceptable color change was observed in all groups. The nanoporous structure of activated charcoal provides it with adsorptive properties, allowing it to absorb extrinsic stains on the composite surface and alter tooth color.³³ A previous study observed that toothpastes containing activated charcoal had higher whitening effects,³⁴ which is consistent with our findings. However, studies on charcoal-containing whitening mouth rinses remain limited. The whiteness change in the LAW group may be attributed to tetrasodium pyrophosphate, which removes extrinsic stains from the surface.³⁵ The superiority of the SWP group in terms of color change may result from bromelain, which breaks down oxidized protein molecules forming extrinsic stains. In addition, the COW group may have had an acceptable effect in whitening because it contained pyrophosphate like the LAW group.

Chemical agents used during whitening not only affect teeth but may also influence existing restorations, potentially causing color changes due to their organic matrix content. Whitening mouth rinses have become increasingly popular because of their low cost and easy accessibility. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate their effects not only on teeth but also on composite restorations. Most studies have examined whitening mouth rinses on artificially stained composites, leading to controversial results.^{36,37} However, such studies can only evaluate the ability of whitening mouth rinses to remove surface stains. In our study, artificial staining was not performed in order to accurately evaluate the real whitening effects of whitening mouth rinses. In studies examining the color changes of composites, the ΔE_{00} index was generally found to be below the acceptable threshold.^{38,39} In contrast, in our study, all groups except the control group were above the acceptable threshold. This may be due to the amount of composite matrix, the degree of polymerization of the resin matrix, and the different active ingredients in the whitening products.

A recent study reported that hydrogen peroxide- and carbamide peroxide-containing whitening mouth rinses caused color changes in composite resins.⁴⁰ In contrast to this result, our study showed that even though our groups did not contain peroxide, they

produced acceptable color differences. This suggests that active charcoal, bromelain derived from pineapple, and pyrophosphate derivatives may provide whitening effects on composites comparable to those of peroxides.

In our study, the mouth rinse cycle procedure was applied according to the manufacturers' recommendations. To simulate daily mouth rinse use, specimens were continuously shaken in 25 mL of mouth rinse for 60 seconds, rinsed under running water for 30 seconds, and then shaken again for 60 seconds. Manufacturers' usage instructions should inform consumers about the importance of adhering to the recommended frequency and application duration of products, as consumers may tend to use whitening products more frequently and for longer durations. Due to the harmful effects of long-term use of mouthwashes, dentists should prescribe teeth whitening products.

As with every in vitro study, our study also has limitations. The current study has limitations such as not being able to exactly mimic the real oral environment and the lack of a cleansing effect of saliva. To better analyze the effects of whitening mouth rinses, more studies should be conducted under clinical conditions. Furthermore, with the increasing interest in whitening, new whitening methods will be developed, and future research should address these factors.

5. Conclusion

The results obtained within the limits of this in vitro study are as follows: Non-hydrogen peroxide whitening mouthrinses caused perceptible and, in most cases, clinically acceptable color changes on nano-hybrid composite resin after a 4-week simulation. Four products (LAW, COW, CPWC, SWP) exceeded the acceptability threshold, with SWP producing the greatest change in both ΔE_{00} and $\Delta W_{1\Delta}$. Clinicians should consider these potential effects when recommending such products to patients with anterior composite restorations, particularly when long-term esthetic stability is important.

References

- Garcia-Godoy F, Garcia-Godoy A, Garcia-Godoy F. Effect of bleaching gels on the surface roughness, hardness, and micromorphology of composites. *Gen Dent*. 2002;50:247-50.
- Donly KJ, Segura A, Henson T, Barker ML, Gerlach RW. Randomized controlled trial of professional at home tooth whitening in teenagers. *Gen Dent*. 2007;55:669-674
- Miranda Dde A, Bertoldo CE, Aguiar FH, Lima DA, Lovadino JR. Effects of mouthwashes on Knoop hardness and surface roughness of dental composites after different immersion times. *Braz Oral Res*. 2011;25:168-73.
- Gerlach RW, Tucker HL, Anastasia MK, Barker ML. Clinical trial comparing 2 hydrogen peroxide tooth whitening systems strips vs prerinse. *Compend Contin Educ Dent*. 2005;26:874-878.
- Pithon MM, Rodrigues AC, Sousa EL, Santos LP, Soares NS. Do mouthwashes with and without bleaching agents degrade the force of elastomeric chains? *Angle Orthod*. 2013;83:712-717.
- Oliveira J, Sarlo RS, Bresciani E, Caneppele T. Whitening efficacy of whitening mouth rinses used alone or in conjunction with carbamide peroxide home whitening. *Oper Dent*. 2017;42:319-326.
- Lima JP, Melo MA, Passos VF, Braga CL, Rodrigues LK, Santiago SL. Dentin erosion by whitening mouthwash associated to toothbrushing abrasion: a focus variation 3D scanning microscopy study. *Microsc Res Tech*. 2013;76:904-908.
- Consolaro A. Mouthwashes with hydrogen peroxide are carcinogenic, but are freely indicated on the internet: warn your patients! *Dental Press J Orthod*. 2013;18:5-12.
- Brooks JK. Chemical burn to the gingiva after misuse of an over-the-counter oral whitening mouthwash. *Gen Dent*. 2017;65:34-36.
- Lima FG, Rotta TA, Penso S, Meireles SS, Demarco FF. In vitro evaluation of the whitening effect of mouth rinses containing hydrogen peroxide. *Braz Oral Res*. 2012;26:269-274.
- Gasparri F, Schemehorn BR, Zanardi A. Efficacy of teeth whitening with a mouthwash: in vitro and in vivo approaches. *J Clin Dent*. 2018; 29:13-17.
- Rosentritt M, Lang R, Plein T, Behr M, Handel G. Discoloration of restorative materials after bleaching application. *Quintessence Int*. 2005;36:33-39
- Hannig C, Duong S, Becker K, Brunner E, Kahler E, Attin T. Effect of bleaching on subsurface micro- hardness of composite and a polyacid modified composite. *Dent Mater*. 2007;23:198-203.
- Um CM, Ruyter IE. Staining of resin-based veneering materials with coffee and tea. *Quintessence Int*. 1991;22(5):377-386.
- Asmussen E, Hansen EK. Surface discoloration of restorative resins in relation to surface softening and oral hygiene. *Scand J Dent Res*. 1986;94(2):174-177.
- Dietschi D, Campanile G, Holz J, Meyer JM. Comparison of the color stability of ten new-generation composites: an in vitro study. *Dent Mater*. 1994;10(6):353-362.
- Karadas M, Alkurt M, Duymus Z. Effects of hydrogen peroxidebased mouthwashes on color changes of stained direct composite resins. *J Restor Dent*. 2016;4:11.
- Azarpazhooh A, Limeback H. The application of ozone in dentistry: a systematic review of literature. *J Dent*. 2008;36(2):104-116.
- Paravina RD, Ghinea R, Herrera LJ, et al. Color difference thresholds in dentistry. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2015;27(Suppl 1):S1-S9.
- Perez MM, Herrera LJ, Carrillo F, et al. Whiteness difference thresholds in dentistry. *Dent Mater*. 2019;35(2):292-297
- Paravina RD, Perez MM, Ghinea R. Acceptability and perceptibility thresholds in dentistry: A comprehensive review of clinical and research applications. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2019;31(2):103-112.
- Ntovas P, Masouras K, Lagouvardos P. Efficacy of non-hydrogen peroxide mouthrinses on tooth whitening: An in vitro study. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2021;33(7):1059-1065.
- He WH, Park CJ, Byun S, Tan D, Lin CY, Chee W. Evaluating the relationship between tooth color and enamel thickness, using twin flash photography, cross-polarization photography, and spectrophotometer. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2020;32(1):91-101.
- Korkut B, Dokumacigil G, Murat N, Atali PY, Tarcin B, Gocmen GB. Effect of Polymerization on the Color of Resin Composites. *Oper Dent*. 2022;47:514-526.
- Meireles SS, de Sousa JP, Lins RBE, Sampaio FC. Efficacy of whitening toothpaste containing blue covarine: A double-blind controlled randomized clinical trial. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2021;33(2):341-350.
- Gomez-Polo C, Portillo Munoz M, Lorenzo Luengo MC, Vicente P, Galindo P, Martin Casado AM. Comparison of the CIE Lab and CIEDE2000 color difference formulas. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2016;115(1):65-70.
- Li K, Chen S, Wang J, Xiao X, Song Z, Liu S. Tooth whitening: Current status and prospects. *Odontology*. 2024;112:700-710.

29. Munchow EA, Hamann HJ, Carvajal MT, Pinal R, Bottino MC. Stain removal effect of novel papain- and bromelain-containing gels applied to enamel. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2016;20(8):2315-2320.
30. Eimar H, Siciliano R, Abdallah MN, Nader SA, Amin WM, Martinez PP, et al. Hydrogen peroxide whitens teeth by oxidizing the organic structure. *J Dent.* 2012;40:e25-33.
31. Tredwin CJ, Naik S, Lewis NJ, Scully C. Hydrogen peroxide tooth-whitening (bleaching) products: review of adverse effects and safety issues. *Br Dent J.* 2006;200:371-376.
32. Bilgili Can D, Özarslan M. Effect Of Whitening Mouthwash On Color Change Of Discolored Bulk-fill Composite Resins. *Cumhuriyet Dent J.* 2022;25:108-113.
33. Vaz VTP, Jubilato DP, Oliveira MRM, Bortolatto JF, Floros MC, Dantas AAR, Oliveira Junior OB. Whitening toothpaste containing activated charcoal, blue covarine, hydrogen peroxide or microbeads: Which one is the most effective? *J Appl Oral Sci.* 2019;27:e20180051.
34. Aydin N, Karaoglanoglu S, Oktay EA, Ersöz B. Determination of the whitening effect of toothpastes on human teeth. *Odovtos Int J Dent Sci.* 2022;24(1):67-75.
35. Hararli OT, Barutçigil C. Color recovery effect of commercial mouth rinses on a discolored composite. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2014;26(4):256-263.
36. Atik E, Kalyoncuoğlu ÜT. The effect of whitening agents (whitening rinse and carbamide peroxide) on stained flowable and packable composite aligner attachments. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2025;29(4):1-13.
37. Celik N, Iscan Yapar M. Colour stability of stained composite resins after brushing with whitening toothpaste. *Int J Dent Hyg.* 2021;19(4):413-420.
38. Pecho OE, Martos J, Pinto KVA, Pinto KVA, Baldissera RA. Effect of hydrogen peroxide on color and whiteness of resin based composites. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2019;31:132-139.
39. Paravina RD, Ghinea R, Herrera LJ, Bona AD, Igiel C, Linninger M, et al. Color difference thresholds in dentistry. *J Esthet Restor Dent.* 2015;27 Suppl 1:S1-9.
40. Savic-Stankovic T, Karadzic B, Komlenic V, Stasic J, Petrovic V, Ilic J, Miletic V. Effects of whitening gels on color and surface properties of a microhybrid and nanohybrid composite. *Dent Mater J.* 2021;40:1380-7.

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CRedit Author Statement

Elif Varlı Tekingür contributed to the study design, analysis, and interpretation and drafted, critically revised the manuscript, and approved the final version of the manuscript. Emin Alper Özer contributed to the study design.

Conflict of Interest

The author has stated explicitly that there are no conflict of interests in connection with this article.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Case Report

Treatment and 18-month Follow-up of Trauma-induced Alveolar Bone Fracture and Lateral Luxation: A Case Report

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CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Prompt repositioning, appropriate splinting, and timely endodontic treatment are essential for managing alveolar fractures with luxation. Maintaining good oral hygiene and regular follow-up significantly influence long-term prognosis and help prevent post-traumatic complications.

ABSTRACT

Traumatic dental injuries are emergencies requiring prompt intervention to prevent complications. This case report presents the endodontic management and 18-month follow-up of a 32-year-old male who suffered an alveolar fracture and lateral luxation of maxillary anterior teeth due to workplace trauma. Clinical examination revealed lacerations, buccal displacement of roots, and palatal displacement of crowns. Manual repositioning and semirigid fiber splinting were performed. Endodontic treatment was initiated on tooth 11 after loss of vitality. Despite initial stabilization and favorable healing, 18-month follow-up revealed pulp necrosis and periapical pathology in tooth 13 and persistent mobility in multiple teeth, likely due to trauma severity and poor oral hygiene. This case emphasizes the importance of early diagnosis, proper repositioning, splinting, endodontic intervention, and strict oral hygiene for optimal long-term outcomes in dentoalveolar trauma.

1. Introduction

Oral traumatic injuries account for approximately 5% of all bodily injuries, with 95% being dental traumas.¹⁻³ With respect to the intensity and direction of the applied force, injuries may affect only the teeth or may involve the surrounding soft tissues and maxillary or mandibular alveolar bone.⁴

Dentoalveolar traumas typically occur due to falls, sports injuries, assaults, or traffic accidents and most frequently involve the anterior teeth, particularly the maxillary central incisors.^{5,6} These injuries include enamel cracks, complicated and uncomplicated crown and crown-root fractures, root and alveolar fractures, concussion, subluxation, extrusive-intrusive and lateral luxation, and avulsion.⁷ Crown fractures and luxation injuries are the most common types.⁸

Luxation injuries are the most frequent form of periodontal tissue trauma.⁹ Lateral luxation refers to the displacement of a tooth in a direction other than its axial orientation.¹⁰ The diagnosis of luxation is based on clinical and radiographic findings; the crowns of laterally luxated teeth are typically displaced palatally, often resulting in fracture or fragmentation of the labial alveolar bone and significant damage to the periodontal ligament.⁹ The apex of the tooth may become locked within the bone. Owing to the severance of the neurovascular bundle, pulp necrosis is common in mature teeth with closed apices following lateral luxation.

Periodontal complications include external root resorption, marginal bone loss, and ankylosis, particularly when repositioning is delayed or improperly performed.¹¹ Treatment of traumatic dental injuries is complex and challenging; thus, accurate diagnosis, appropriate treatment planning, and regular follow-up are essential for favorable clinical outcomes.⁹

According to current treatment guidelines (International Association of Dental Traumatology – IADT), a flexible splint should be applied for approximately four weeks following repositioning to promote periodontal ligament healing.⁷ Furthermore, endodontic treatment is recommended for teeth with closed apices to prevent root resorption.¹¹

This case report presents endodontic treatment and 18-month follow-up of a patient with an alveolar bone fracture of the maxillary buccal cortex and lateral luxation of the maxillary incisors due to trauma.

2. Case Presentation

A 32-year-old healthy male patient presented to the Department of Endodontics, Faculty of Dentistry, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, three days after a workplace accident. Extraoral examination revealed laceration and edema of the lower lip and ecchymosis of the upper lip. Intraoral examination revealed an alveolar fracture of the maxillary buccal cortex and lateral luxation of teeth 11, 12, and 13. Hemorrhagic and disrupted soft tissues were observed in the anterior maxillary region (Fig. 1).

As the roots of the affected teeth were displaced buccally and the incisal edges were displaced palatally, the teeth were repositioned buccally before the fractured segment was placed. Closed reduction was performed manually, and the segment was stabilized anatomically. Semirigid fiber splinting (Interlig™, Angelus, Brazil) was applied from the right to the left first premolars using light-cured composite resin (Fig. 2). Postoperatively, the patient was prescribed antibiotics [amoxicillin

Fig. 1. Extraoral and intraoral photographs and panoramic radiograph of the patient

(1000 mg, 2x/day)] and analgesics [ibuprofen 600 mg, 2x/day]. The patient was advised to avoid trauma, maintain a soft and liquid diet, practice good oral hygiene, and refrain from biting.

At the 14-day follow-up, vitality testing was repeated, and root canal treatment was performed on nonvital tooth 11. The semirigid splint was removed after four weeks (Fig. 3).

At the 6-month follow-up, clinical and radiographic evaluations revealed asymptomatic teeth, positive vitality responses in teeth 12 and 13, and no adverse findings at the fracture site. However, the patient exhibited poor oral hygiene and was educated accordingly (Fig. 4).

At the 18-month follow-up, vitality testing revealed necrosis in tooth 13 with the presence of a periapical lesion on panoramic radiograph and slight mobility. Teeth 11 and 21 also showed mobility, and oral hygiene remained poor (Fig. 5). Despite this, the patient reported satisfaction with the functional and aesthetic outcomes of the treated teeth. Follow-up is ongoing.

3. Discussion

Traumatic dental injuries may result from falls, vehicular accidents, sports activities, and impacts from foreign objects. The extent of damage depends on factors such as trauma severity, characteristics of the impacting object, direction of the force, capacity of soft tissues to absorb impact, and the dental-occlusal relationship.^{5,12} These injuries predominantly affect the maxillary anterior region, particularly the central incisors, largely due to the maxilla enclosing and protecting the mandible in the resting and

Fig. 2. Application of the fiber splint

Fig. 3. Root canal treatment on tooth 11 and intraoral image after splinting

occlusal positions.^{13,14}

Trauma to the anterior teeth may lead to aesthetic, functional, and phonetic issues. Treatment planning should consider patient-specific factors such as age, systemic health, type of trauma, and involved tissues.⁶ Maxillary alveolar fractures often result from direct or indirect forces transmitted from the mandible and commonly involve 2–3 teeth. These injuries may be accompanied by soft tissue trauma. Although teeth within the fractured segment are often immobile, dislocation or luxation may still occur.^{6–15} Clinical indicators of alveolar fracture include segment mobility, disruption of the dental arch, and occlusal discrepancies.^{6,16}

In the present case, trauma to the anterior maxilla led to an alveolar process fracture and lateral luxation of incisors with significant soft tissue damage. Treatment of alveolar fractures should begin promptly, as delays are associated with an increased risk of complications and reduced surgical success.⁴ Repositioning within the first hour of trauma significantly reduces the risk of pulpal complications.¹⁵

The primary objective of treatment is to anatomically reposition and stabilize the fractured segment, often achieved through manual pressure. In cases where incisal edges are displaced buccally, correcting this displacement is essential prior to reduction.^{5,17} In this case, closed reduction and stabilization were successfully performed. Lateral luxation is among the most frequent injuries to permanent teeth and is commonly associated with pulp necrosis. If not properly managed, complications such as inflammatory resorption and chronic apical periodontitis may

Fig. 4. Intraoral photographs of the patient at the 6-month follow-up

Fig. 5. Clinical and radiographic images obtained after 18 months of follow-up

arise, highlighting the need for long-term follow-up.¹²

Stabilization of displaced teeth is a critical step in trauma management. Teeth should be splinted to adjacent stable teeth to prevent damage from masticatory forces.¹⁸ Proper repositioning and stabilization also support periodontal and neurovascular healing.¹⁹ Flexible splinting is considered best practice, as it allows physiological movement, reduces discomfort, increases patient compliance, and protects against further trauma.²⁰

Several splinting methods are used in dentoalveolar trauma management, including wire composites, fiber splints, and titanium splints. Among these, flexible materials are preferred.^{5,6,21} Fiber splints offer the additional benefits of aesthetics, biocompatibility, and ease of application.²¹ In the present case, a semirigid fiber splint was used to achieve stabilization.

The ideal duration of splinting varies with the type of trauma. For alveolar fractures and lateral luxation, four weeks is generally sufficient. In cases with poor periodontal support or marginal bone fragmentation, this period may need to be extended.⁹ However, prolonged splinting is associated with risks such as root and bone resorption, pulp necrosis, and ankylosis. Studies have shown no additional benefit in splinting non-dislocated teeth or extending splinting beyond four weeks.²² Teeth within fractured segments that lose vitality should undergo endodontic treatment within two weeks.⁷ In this case, the splint was removed after four weeks, and endodontic treatment was performed within the recommended timeframe.

Post-trauma instructions, such as a soft diet for two weeks, soft brushing after meals, and 0.1% chlorhexidine rinses for soft tissue injuries, are critical for optimal healing.⁷

Despite appropriate initial management, complications following dentoalveolar trauma can include marginal bone loss, pulp necrosis and infection, apical periodontitis, ankylosis, root resorption, tooth loss, splint-related periodontal problems, and malocclusion.^{7,23} The rate of post-traumatic pulp necrosis is reported to range from 20% to 50%.^{24,25} In this case, 18-month follow-up revealed pulp necrosis and apical periodontitis in tooth 13. Long-term mobility was observed in several teeth, likely due to the severity of the initial trauma and poor oral hygiene. Gingival recession and bone loss were also noted, emphasizing the importance of appropriate post-traumatic care.

This case highlights the critical role of early diagnosis, rapid and accurate repositioning, and consistent oral hygiene in achieving favorable long-term outcomes following alveolar fractures and lateral luxation injuries.

4. Conclusion

Dental trauma is a significant emergency involving hard and soft tissues of the teeth, often resulting from accidents. Early diagnosis, correct treatment protocols, and long-term clinical and radiographic monitoring of permanent dental injuries are crucial for managing potential complications.

References

1. Andersson L. Epidemiology of traumatic dental injuries. *J Endod.* 2013; 39:S25.
2. Mahmoodi B, Rahimi-Nedjat R, Weusmann J, Azaripour A, Walter C, Willershausen B. Traumatic dental injuries in a university hospital: A four-year retrospective study. *BMC Oral Health.* 2015; 15:139.
3. Alnaggar D, Andersson L. Emergency management of traumatic dental injuries in 42 countries. *Dent Traumatol.* 2015; 31:89-96.
4. Andreasen JO, Andreasen FM. *Classification, etiology and epidemiology.* In: Textbook and Color Atlas of Traumatic Injuries. Copenhagen, Denmark: Munksgaard; 1994:151-180.
5. İrdem HÖ, Canpolat N, Yıldırım G. Alveolar proses fraktürünün semi-rigid fiksasyon ile tedavisi: Bir olgu sunumu. *Selcuk Dent J.* 2017;4:106-109.
6. Doğan G, Küçükkolbaşı H, Durmuş E, Kalaycı A. Dentoalveolar yaralanmalarda erken tedavi uygulamasının prognoz açısından önemi: Olgu sunumu. *Selcuk Dent J.* 2023;10(4):343-349.
7. Levin L, Day PF, Hicks L. International Association of Dental Traumatology guidelines for the management of traumatic dental injuries: General introduction. *Dent Traumatol.* 2020;36(4):309-313.

8. Khan MK, Jindal MK. Successful treatment of laterally luxated teeth with traumatic occlusion in adolescent patient by single arch fixed orthodontic therapy: A case-report. *Sci Dent J*. 2022, 6(2):87–93.
9. De RM, De RA, Queiroz AM, Nelson FP. Management of a complex dentoalveolar trauma: A case report. *Braz Dent J*. 2009, 20(3):259–262.
10. DiAngelis AJ, Andreasen JO, Ebeleseder KA. International Association of Dental Traumatology guidelines for the management of traumatic dental injuries: 1. Fractures and luxations of permanent teeth. *Dent Traumatol*. 2012, 28(1):2–12.
11. Soares PBF, Vilela ABF, Moura CCG. Lateral luxation of incisor – A case report of using a new cone-beam computed tomography software and reposition guideline. *Braz Dent J*. 2020, 31(3):337–343.
12. Goswami M, Eranhikkal A. Management of traumatic dental injuries using different types of splints: A case series. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2020, 13(2):199–202.
13. Ezirganlı Ş, Kapdan A, Erdoğan MŞ, Kırmalı. Travmatik olarak intrüze olan maksiller sürekli kesici dişlere tedavi yaklaşımı: İki olgu sunumu. *Acıbadem Univ Sağlık Bilim Derg*. 2011, 2(4):224–227.
14. Leroy RL, Aps JK, Raes FM. A multidisciplinary treatment approach to a complicated maxillary dental trauma: A case report. *Endod Dent Traumatol*. 2000, 16:138–142.
15. Tagar H, Djemal S. Oral surgery II: Part 1. Acute management of dentoalveolar trauma. *Br Dent J*. 2017, 223(6):407–416.
16. Leathers RD, Gowans RE. Office-based management of dental alveolar trauma. *Atlas Oral Maxillofac Surg Clin N Am*. 2013, 21:185–197.
17. Padilla RR, Felsenfeld AL. Treatment and prevention of alveolar fractures and related injuries. *J Craniomaxillofac Trauma*. 1997, 3(2):22–27.
18. Çetin AR, Özcan E. Travma geçirmiş anterior dişlerde gelişen kök kırıklarında restoratif tedavi yaklaşımı. *SDÜ Sağlık Bilimleri Enstit Derg*. 2013, 4(3):125–129.
19. American Academy on Pediatric Dentistry Council on Clinical Affairs. Guideline on management of acute dental trauma. *Pediatr Dent*. 2008, 30:175–183.
20. Honório HM, de Alencar CR, Pereira JES. Posttraumatic displacement management: Lateral luxation and alveolar bone fracture in young permanent teeth with 5 years of follow-up. *Case Rep Dent*. 2015, 2015:634237.
21. Von AT. Splinting of traumatized teeth with focus on adhesive techniques. *J Calif Dent Assoc*. 2005, 33:409–414.
22. American Association of Endodontists. Guidelines for the management of traumatic dental injuries: 1. Fractures and luxations of permanent teeth. *Dent Traumatol*. 2012, 28:2–12.
23. Zvi G, Eli P, Doron N, Shaul L. Alveolar bone fracture: Pathognomonic sign for clinical diagnosis. *Open Dent J*. 2017, 11:8–14.
24. Alharbi MA, Alghamdi A, Kattan SA. The incidence of devitalization of vital teeth associated with pathologies of the jaws following surgical intervention: A mixed-case study. *J Contemp Dent Pract*. 2023, 24(10):750–756.
25. Aldrigui JM, Cadioli IC, Mendes FM. Predictive factors for pulp necrosis in traumatized primary incisors: A longitudinal study. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2013, 23(6):460–469.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.